

Network of European Research Infrastructures for Earthquake Risk Assessment and Mitigation

Report

D15.1 Developed integrated field monitoring technologies

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Author:	VCE, EUCENTRE, AIT, AUTH, KU Leuven

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Summary

The deliverable 15.1 concerns the application of field monitoring technologies to European buildings and aggregates. The publication is plugged in the EU-funded NERA research project (FP7, N. 262330), in the Work Package Joint Research Activities 5: Vulnerability assessment from field monitoring.

NERA is the acronym of "Network of European Research Infrastructures for Earthquake Risk Assessment and Mitigation". The project runs from the 1st November 2010, up to the 31st October 2014.

The main goals of the project are:

1. Easing the synergies between the European key-research-infrastructures, in order to achieve a better prevention from the earthquake hazards;
2. Create analytical tools and mobile facilities for the construction sites characterization, based on vulnerability assessments;
3. Develop instruments and performing hazard and risk assessment, data processing and data dissemination
4. Support the reduction of vulnerability due to earthquake, of European citizens and constructions.
5. Foster the international collaboration activities and further integration of the research field

The seismic risk is mainly the product of three components: 1) the probability that an earthquake of a predefined magnitude (or return period) has to occur; 2) the vulnerability meant as the attitude of an element to be damaged by to a certain strain; 3) the exposed value expressed in terms of human life and goods.

The risk assessment cannot apart from the estimation of these components as well as the risk mitigation can only act on the component 2) and 3).

The risk could be indeed mitigated by minimizing the exposed value (buildings or people), or the vulnerability.

The key point of the actual Work Package involve indeed the system identification of several kinds of buildings, by means of the most modern site monitoring, in order to characterize their fragility.

In emergency situation, the public administration in charge will be aware to send rescues where the seismic risk is higher, in other words where the buildings have also a higher vulnerability.

Data for the most common building typologies within the inventory of European buildings developed in NA7 are obtained using the field monitoring techniques codified in NA6. These building typologies treated in the actual deliverable comprise mainly masonry buildings and masonry building aggregates located in the city of Vienna. Treated as a special case, the analysis performed on massive a concrete building, constructed in the period previous to the 2nd World War

1. Introduction

The argumentation of the deliverable follow a logic path: in the section 2. "Uses of traditional technologies" (accelerometers), several accelerometers are engaged to perform the system identification of buildings located in different sites.

In the third chapter "Use of advanced technology (LDV)", the Laser Doppler Vibrometer is introduced. In detail, it has been used to sense the difference of structural retrofitting intervention on the global dynamic behavior of the analyzed building.

The 4th chapter "Validation of the technology" is focused at showing the sensitivity of the monitoring system installed, by comparing different stages of demolition.

In the last chapter, the implementation of all the described techniques is applied to the Falkturm, a second world war massive anti-craft construction.

2. Contributions from VCE

2.1 Use of traditional technologies (accelerometers)

2.1.1 Assessments of historic residential buildings based on experimental investigations

In the urban areas of Central Europe a noticeable amount of residential buildings are older than 90 years. For instance in the city center of the Austrian capital Vienna approximately 32.000 houses were erected between 1850 and 1918, which is about one third of the present-day stock of buildings. Mostly, these structures have been retained unchanged without considerable structural improvement since decades. Many of these objects are landmarked, and space is limited for the construction of new houses, and thus, in the last twenty years unused attics of these historic buildings were converted into new apartments in order to recreate additional living space.

The reconstruction and development of attics in historic buildings is regulated in national standards. Since recent investigations have revealed that in Central Europe the earthquake hazard was underestimated considerably, these regulations were tightened in spring 2006 by increasing the effective earthquake loads. In for the assessment of sufficient seismic resistance of existing buildings the following cases are distinguished:

- Up to an additional vertical load of 7.2 kN/m² a simplified seismic analysis is permitted.
- For larger additional loads sophisticated seismic analysis procedures must be applied.

The simplified analysis is applicable only for lightweight constructions with a small increase of vertical loads. However, in the vast majority of cases the earthquake resistance of the structure to be remodeled must be verified by means of complex numerical methods considering large uncertainties, and the expenses for most reconstructions increase dramatically. The actual condition of the masonry of old buildings is in general hardly known, and the structural system and parameters are in general not well documented. There is also a lack of information on parameters of construction material utilized in ancient houses. It is a matter of fact that the new regulations led to a major decline of reconstruction of historic buildings and thus, to economic disadvantages for the real estate market.

Hence, there exists a high demand for an economic and sufficient accurate seismic analysis, which is relatively easy to implement. In this paper a simplified method based on combined experimental – numerical analysis is presented.

2.1.1.1 Methodology

2.1.1.1.1 In situ measurements

Seismic analyses are based on basic dynamic parameters of the considered object such as natural frequencies and the corresponding mode shapes. For existing buildings these parameters are determined beneficially from data recorded by in-situ measurements, in particular when structural system and utilized materials are unknown. It is proposed to utilize accelerometers, which are distributed on the story levels on top of each other. As an example Figure 1 shows the position of accelerometers in an actual investigated residential building in Vienna. The sensors are placed next to the staircase because the apartments are occupied, and thus cannot be entered without additional logistic effort. Advantageously, the measurements are performed during the night when foot traffic is low and excitation from engines such as washing machines is very unlikely.

Figure 1: Sensor instrumentation of a residential building.

In tall buildings measurements cannot be conducted simultaneously, because the number of available sensors is customarily limited. For such objects a reference sensor is located in a story, where it remains during the entire measurement period. After each measurement a second accelerometer is moved to a further measuring point at a different story level until the entire building is surveyed. The response of the sensor to be moved is related to the response measured with the reference sensor.

Depending on the type of building and measurement equipment two different analysis techniques based on:

the ambient vibrations response (ambient excitation)

the free vibration response after an impulsive like load applied with a hammer (transient excitation)

may be utilized to evaluate the dynamic parameters.

It is noted that the location of excitation must remain the same when measurements are performed with a reference sensor.

2.1.1.1.2 Signal processing

The dynamic time history response is recorded in three directions. However, if reasonable the evaluation of the data is confined to one building axis, where the structure is most vulnerable, i.e. effects such as torsion or coupled bending torsional vibrations are negligible.

The natural frequencies of the building structure are determined by transforming the time-history signals of each sensor into the frequency domain by Fast-Fourier-Transformation (FFT). Depending on the recorded data the mode shapes are evaluated in the time domain (transient excitation) or in the frequency domain (ambient excitation).

2.1.1.1.3 Transient excitation – time domain

If the building can be excited transiently by means of a hammer the induced free vibration response is utilized to identify the dynamic parameters. The procedure of data processing in the time domain is sketched in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Evaluation of natural frequencies and mode shapes based on transient excitation.

The n -th modal component of the undamped free displacement and acceleration response \bar{w}_n and $\ddot{\bar{w}}_n$ respectively, of a multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) system differ by the square of the n -th natural circular frequency ω_n^2 ,

$$\bar{w}_n = \bar{\phi}_n \cos \omega_n t, \quad \ddot{\bar{w}}_n = -\omega_n^2 \bar{\phi}_n \cos \omega_n t \quad (1)$$

In (1) $\bar{\phi}_n$ denotes the n -th mode shape. Since the maximum amplitude of a mode shape is arbitrary the mode shape can be extracted directly from the acceleration response.

The fractions of the response, which vibrate in the natural frequencies of interest, are extracted by filtering the raw signal. Therefore the raw acceleration response is edited by a band-pass filter of 4th order. The frequency band around the considered natural frequency is very narrow, i.e. the upper and lower boundary of the frequency $f_{u,l}$ are selected according to

$$f_{u,l} = f_n \pm \frac{f_n}{100} \quad (2)$$

This procedure is performed for each identified natural frequency. Subsequently, the extracted time history responses of each story is plotted on top of each other, and at certain time instants the amplitudes are read and combined to the vector $\bar{\phi}_{n,i}$. Note that the floor response must be related to the response recorded with the reference sensor when the measurements of the floor accelerations are conducted at different time instants. Finally, the estimate of the n -th mode shape is determined by averaging,

$$\bar{\phi}_n = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \bar{\phi}_{n,i} \quad (3)$$

In Figure 3 the evaluation of the first bending mode $\bar{\phi}_1$ of an investigated building structure according to the described procedure is shown.

Figure 3: Evaluation of natural frequencies and mode shapes based on transient excitation.

2.1.1.1.4 Ambient excitation – frequency domain

If the ambient vibration response is recorded the mode shapes have to be determined in the frequency domain. For the evaluation of the mode shapes it is necessary to evaluate the phase of the acceleration response. Therefore, the phasing of the response signal of each floor of the building needs to be investigated. In order to increase the reliability of the results this should be done simultaneously for each obtained record. The mode shapes are finally averaged for the different recorded signals.

Figure 4: Evaluation of the fundamental mode of a building structure (frequency domain).

2.1.1.1.5 Finite element model update

An estimate of the distributed stiffness of the investigated building is calculated utilizing the equations of motion for a simplified mechanical model. Thereby, the structure is considered as a MDOF system with lumped masses at each story level. The model of the MDOF system is thereby created as an approximation with several assumptions and can lead to differences to the real structure. To improve the accuracy of the system the dynamic parameters are calibrated with the outcomes from in-situ measurements. Therefore a numerical updating procedure is utilized.

In general finite element model updating can be performed using direct or iterative methods. The former has the advantages, because no iteration is required and measured data are reproduced exactly. However, if the measured data is inaccurate (or correspond to a highly nonlinear system), a model with no physical meaning may be obtained. In contrast, iterative methods are based on a non-linear penalty function, which is minimized through subsequent linear steps, and more computational time is required.

For the procedure proposed in this paper, a sensitivity-based iterative method is utilized [4]. The computational technique is carried out by VCUPDATE, an iterative updating algorithm implemented in Scilab, which is interfaced with the finite element code OpenSees.

2.1.1.1.6 Seismic assessment of existing buildings

The performance of the building under seismic loading is estimated by means of the capacity spectrum method. The simplified mechanical model obtained from the finite element model update procedure is subjected to a pushover analysis, which yields the capacity curve of the structure. The pushover analysis facilitates the consideration of material nonlinearities of the structure. It is therefore scheduled to perform large-scale tests on building structures as well as laboratory tests on masonry material in order to get information about the nonlinear behavior of historic buildings. The initial viscous damping of the building is estimated and an appropriate demand spectrum is consulted. The intersection of demand spectrum and capacity curve renders the initial value of the performance point of the building subjected to a given seismic input, as shown in Figure 5. In an iteration procedure the effective viscous damping coefficient $\zeta_{sys,eff}$ is compared with the initial viscous damping value $\zeta_{initial}$ until a certain convergence criterion is reached. Finally the obtained performance point is an appropriate measure for the evaluation of the seismic hazard of the building.

Figure 5: Capacity curve, demand spectrum, and performance point.

2.1.1.1.7 Seismic assessment of existing buildings with projected reconstruction

Structural changes of projected reconstructions in existing structures such as remodeling of the attic may be considered by change of mass and stiffness in the mechanical model. This can be done without major effort, because the effect of the structural design features can be estimated very quickly. A pushover analysis renders the capacity curve of the modified model, and seismic assessment analysis is carried out. The impact of various preliminary designs on the seismic vulnerability of the structure can be checked.

2.1.1.2 Applications

2.1.1.2.1 Objects

Several existing objects were tested in order to verify the applicability and reliability of the proposed method. The in-situ measurements were preferably performed using transient excitation. In Table 1 the investigated structures, their dimension and employed building material are listed. Furthermore, first and second natural frequencies f_1 and f_2 , respectively, in two directions (E-W: east-west, N-S: north-south) of the objects are given in the same table.

Table 1: Investigated structures – general information and natural frequencies determined from measured data.

location	dimensions [m]	height [m]	building material	$f_{1,E-W}$ [Hz]	$f_{2,E-W}$ [Hz]	$f_{1,N-S}$ [Hz]	$f_{2,N-S}$ [Hz]
1 Riglergasse 10, Vienna	18 x 16	23.2	masonry	2.42	6.75	-	-
2 Diesterwegg. 4, Vienna	12 x 24	16.7	masonry	3.61	11.30	-	-
3 Istanbul I – Fenerbaçe	18 x 31	14.5	RC	5.10	10.20	5.43	19.39
4 Istanbul II – Fenerbaçe	19 x 21	17.0	RC	4.85	-	5.27	10.33
5 Istanbul III – Galatasaray	4 x 14	12.0	masonry	3.02	7.16	-	-
6 Istanbul IV – Fenerbaçe	10 x 20	24.0	RC	1.75	7.15	2.53	10.07
7 Istanbul V – Fenerbaçe	18 x 18	37.0	RC	1.61	7.58	1.63	6.06
8 Bucharest – Hotel Ibis	50 x 17	25.0	RC	-	-	3.03	23.29

2.1.1.2.2 Results

In the following object 1 of Table 1 (Riglergasse 10, Vienna) is examined. Both ambient excited and transient excited building response are utilized for the evaluation of this building. Measurements were performed during a long period with a sampling rate of 500 Hz. This large sampling rate was selected to window the signal with small time steps. A part of a record and the windowing of the signal are shown in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: Transient (a) and ambient (b) windows with a length of 8 s for the acceleration record at the first floor of the investigated residential building (Riglergasse 10, 1180 Vienna).

The structural mass was estimated consulting design documents, and lumped to the story levels. The first and second mode shape, the story masses, and the story stiffness are specified in Figure 7. The stiffness of the mechanical model was determined by application of the mentioned indirect finite element update procedure.

Figure 7: Final model of the investigated residential building (Riglergasse 10, 1180 Vienna), mode shapes (east - west direction) for the corresponding frequencies.

These results constitute the structural input values for the capacity design method. The structural model shown in Figure 7 is subjected to a static pushover analysis. In order to consider the global nonlinear behavior of the masonry buildings it is scheduled to perform large-scale in-situ pushover tests on real structures. The outcomes of these tests will be utilized to calibrate the numerical pushover analysis. The nonlinear material parameters will be verified using several laboratory-tests on undisturbed masonry specimens.

2.1.1.2.3 Further developments

During the evaluation of the dynamic parameters for the building structures listed in Table 1 some difficulties have emerged, which should be resolved in future research work.

- The evaluation of natural frequencies for residential buildings can be very cumbersome due to the fact that the structure may have no strongly developed vibration behavior. Thus it might be necessary to use different methods for their identification in addition such as the stochastic subspace method.
- During the in-situ measurements attention has to be paid to internal excitation (e.g. generators, washing machines), as they can strongly affect the measurement results.
- For the evaluation of the mode shapes in the frequency domain it is advantageous to have ambient signals only. This is hardly to realize because of locally induced vibrations (e.g. by inhabitants).
- The evaluation of mode shapes based on the response induced by impulse loading seems to be more reliable if the structure is rather small, because the initiated free vibrations can be recognized clearly at each sensor location. When there are not enough sensors available to record the induced vibrations simultaneously at all story levels this method leads to reliable results only when the excitation signal can be repeated for each measurement with different locations of the accelerometer.

- For the investigated structures only the first two natural frequencies and mode shapes could be determined. The accuracy of the finite element model update procedure can be increased, if at least the third natural frequency and mode shape is included.

2.1.1.3 Considerations

In recent years seismic assessment analysis of existing residential buildings has become a major issue for the construction industry. The release of uniform regulations for whole Europe has led to changes in the validation of the existing structures. Particular the evaluation of the vulnerability of historic residential houses is very difficult to realize. A combined numerical - experimental analysis is the most promising approach to assess these objects. In this paper such a procedure is proposed, which is based on in-situ measurements of the considered object. Evaluation of the recorded vibration response renders the dynamic parameters such as natural frequencies and mode shapes. Procedures in the time and frequencies domain are suggested, depending on the type of measurement. The stiffness of the structure is estimated utilizing a finite element model update procedure. Subsequently, the seismic vulnerability of the building is verified utilizing capacity spectra. The structural resistance of existing buildings after reconstruction, such as erection of additional apartments in empty attics, can be done by the same procedure.

2.1.2 Assessment of the global dynamic behaviour of a historic residential brick-masonry building in Vienna

In the past no particular attention was paid to the seismic assessment of historic masonry buildings in Austria. However, recent investigations have revealed that in Central Europe earthquake hazard has been underestimated considerably, and subsequently, regulations concerning the seismic hazard have been tightened. As a consequence, the seismic resistance of most of the historic masonry buildings in the Austrian capital Vienna cannot be verified anymore by common seismic analysis approaches. In recent years this problem started to attract the attention of engineers and scientists.

The structural system of historic buildings can hardly be assessed by traditional methods such as inspection. Thus, certain structural and non-structural elements may not or must not be taken into account for prediction of the seismic resistance of an existing building.

It is of primary interest to quantify the contribution of non-structural walls to the seismic resistance of a building. If structure and material parameters are well defined, the outcomes of numerical studies with and without non-structural walls are set in contrast most effectively. However, this methodology may be used for newer buildings only. In historic buildings the required information about non-structural walls can be extracted only through in-situ investigations. Such investigations implicate the demolition of the non-structural partition walls, and therefore, the considered building needs to be unoccupied. In an experimental investigation of rein-forced concrete buildings by Hans et al. (2005) this methodology has already been approved.

In a unique opportunity, a historic brick masonry building in the city of Vienna was provided for re-search purposes before it was demolished. Within the research project SEISMID (Achs et al. 2011) extensive measurement campaigns were performed on this building to identify the contribution of non-structural partition walls to the global dynamic response.

In the following the test procedure and results of the study on this building are presented.

2.1.2.1 Test object

The test object of the described investigation is a historic masonry building, which was located in the city centre of Vienna, Austria, at the intersection of two side streets named Spittelbreitengasse and Singrienergasse, see Figure 8. It was built about 150 years ago and has been used for housing purposes since then. Figure 9 shows a photograph of the test object.

The three store building with ground floor, first floor, second floor, and an attic had two wings, which were arranged perpendicularly. Only the building wing parallel to the street Spittelbreitengasse had a basement. Its dimensions can be read from Figure 10. The object, which was constructed at the end of the 19th century, had been almost completely preserved in its original condition before the described investigations were started. The non- structural walls were almost periodically distributed on the first and second floor. On the ground floor, which was used as a restaurant, steel beams supported most of these non-structural walls.

Figure 8: Orientation of the test object.

Figure 9: Photograph of the test object.

The walls were made of brick masonry. The ceiling between the basement and the ground floor consisted of brick vaults, whereas the ceilings of the upper stories were constructed of timber beams. Steel bars connected almost all timber beams of the timber ceilings with the load bearing walls.

2.1.2.2 Test procedure and experimental set-up

2.1.2.2.1 Test procedure

A dynamic system identification procedure based on the measurement of the dynamic response was applied. Thereby, the global dynamic parameters of the test object were determined for two different conditions, i.e. for the

- original undisturbed building, and for a
- modified form of the building, where a series of partition walls were removed.

At first, a series of tests was performed on the original undisturbed object. The results extracted from these in-situ measurements represent the structural properties of the building including loadbearing walls, timber ceilings, and non-structural elements such as partition walls. For details on experimental methods for the assessment of the dynamic behaviour of buildings it is referred to Navarro & Oliveira (2006).

Subsequently, the non-structural partition walls were removed in the building wing parallel to the street Singrienergasse as shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

A second test series was conducted in the same manner as it was done in the original building condition.

The material of the demolished walls was placed next to the original wall locations to leave the mass distribution almost in its original condition, see Figure 13. The test section for recording the dynamic response was selected in this wing according to Figure 14.

2.1.2.2.2 Excitation

The building was excited to free vibrations by an impact of a lumped mass applied to the internal load-bearing wall in the attic above the test section. The lumped mass consisted

of a bag filled with 50 kg of gravel. Figure 14 shows the point of application of the impact load within the test section.

Figure 10: Floor plan of the first and second floor; (b) Section A-A representing the building wing parallel to the street Singrienergasse; (c) Section B-B representing the building wing parallel to the street Spittelbreitengasse.

Figure 11: Location of the test section; Partition walls, which have been removed between the test series, are highlighted in red.

Figure 12: Perspective view; Partition walls, which have been removed between the test series, are highlighted in red.

Figure 13: Interior after demolition of the partition walls in the first floor.

Figure 14: Vertical distribution of the acceleration sensors in the

2.1.2.2.3 Instrumentation

The induced free-vibration response of the building was recorded by capacitive accelerometers, which were connected to an A/D converter, controller and data logger. The accelerometers were directly placed and mounted on the external and internal load-bearing walls in windowsills and alcoves of the test section to capture only the global dynamic behavior of the building and to avoid interfering signals from local dynamic effects, see Figure 14. In vertical direction the accelerometers were distributed storey-wise on top of each other. A Cartesian system of coordinates identified the recorded acceleration response components non-ambiguously. As depicted in Figure 14z denotes the vertical direction, whereas x indicates the horizontal coordinate parallel to the street Spittelbreitengasse, and the horizontal coordinate y is parallel to the street Singrienergasse.

2.1.2.2.4 Signal processing and data analysis

After the measurement campaigns, signal processing and data analyses were conducted in the laboratory.

Thereby, the time histories' signals were transformed into the frequency domain by Fast-Fourier-Transformation, which yielded the spectral response.

The signal processing was performed according to a standard evaluation method developed within the SEISMID research project. For details see Achs et al. (2007) and Achs (2011).

2.1.2.3 Experimental results

2.1.2.3.1 Frequency response and mode shapes

The horizontal components of the spectral responses in x -direction are presented in Figure 15 to Figure 18. The corresponding acceleration responses were recorded in the attic (Figure 15 and Figure 16) and on the second floor (Figure 17 and Figure 18), both at the internal (Figure 15 and Figure 17) and an external (Figure 16 and Figure 18) load-bearing wall. In these figures, red lines correspond to the response of the original building with partition walls, and green lines refer to the results of the modified building after removing the partition walls.

The frequency response exhibits pronounced peaks at distinct frequencies. Assuming the absence of harmonic interference signals, these frequencies correspond with the natural frequencies of the structure. It can be seen that for both conditions of the building the peak responses occur at the same frequencies both for the internal and the external load-bearing wall. Thus, it can be concluded that all peaks in the response represent the global building behavior. Furthermore, this result verifies that these walls are coupled through the timber ceilings and the roof structure, because the partition walls have been re-moved in the modified building.

In Table 2 the fundamental natural frequency f_1 of the original building and the modified building is specified, which was identified from Figure 15 to Figure 18. The spectral responses of the modified building show a major reduction of the natural frequencies Df_1 of about 1.3 Hz (52%) when compared to the outcomes of the original building.

2.1.2.3.2 Structural damping

The fundamental modal damping coefficient ζ_1 of the original and modified structure was extracted from the decay of the free vibration response for five recorded response samples. The mean value is considered to be the representative fundamental modal damping coefficient ζ_1 . The individual damping coefficients for each response sample and the mean values are specified in Table 2. It can be seen that ζ_1 of the original structure is 53% lower compared to ζ_1 of the modified structure (Achs 2011).

Figure 15: Acceleration frequency response; Attic, internal loadbearing.

Figure 16: Acceleration frequency response: Attic, external load bearing wall adjacent to the street. Red line: original building. Green line: modified building.

Table 2: Fundamental natural frequency and modal damping coefficient of the original undisturbed and the modified building.

	Fundamental natural frequency f_1 [Hz]	Fundamental damping coefficient ζ_1 [%]
Original building	3.8	5.0
Modified building	2.5	11.7

Figure 17: Acceleration frequency response: Second floor, internal load-bearing wall. Red line: original building. Green line: modified building.

Figure 18: Acceleration frequency response; Second floor, external load-bearing wall adjacent to the street. Red line: original building. Green line: modified building.

2.1.2.4 Numerical analysis

2.1.2.4.1 Verification of the dynamic parameters

A three-dimensional Finite-Element model was generated by means of the Finite-Element code ANSYS.

Thereby, load-bearing walls, non-structural partition walls, and timber ceilings were modeled with shell elements. Linear elastic structural properties of the structure were considered. The timber ceilings were connected with hinges to the load-bearing walls. Slight coupling of the test object with the adjacent buildings at both end walls was considered via spring-damper elements distributed perpendicular and parallel to the end walls.

The material parameters were calibrated so that the numerically derived and experimentally identified natural frequencies of the original undisturbed building coincide roughly, see Table 3. It turned out that the calibrated material parameters are of the same magnitude with corresponding parameters obtained from experimental tests and numerical homogenization procedures (Furtmüller 2010, Furtmüller & Adam 2011, Furtmüller et al. 2012). Further details of the numerical model and applied material parameters can be found in Achs (2011).

The natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes of the numerical model of the original and the modified building structure were determined using the modal analysis tool of the Finite-Element code.

The results listed in Table 4 show that also the first and the third natural frequency of the numerical model of the modified structure without partition walls are in good agreement with the experimentally determined counterparts. This outcome supports on the one hand the quality of the applied test and identification procedure, and on the other hand the accuracy of the numerical model. However, the numerical analysis underestimates the second global natural frequency considerably, compare with Table 4. A further goal of the numerical analyses was the identification of the spatial distribution of the mode shapes, which were known only at discrete points from measurements. Of particular interest were the first two mode shapes of the modified building, since the corresponding peaks in the frequency response are closely spaced, compare e.g. with Figure 15.

Mode number	Natural frequency [Hz]	
	Measurement	Numerical analysis
1	3.8	3.78
2	4.2	4.29
3	4.6	4.67

Table 3: Natural frequencies of the original undisturbed building.

Mode number	Natural frequency [Hz]	
	Measurement	Numerical analysis
1	2.5	2.61
2	3.1	3.77
3	4.1	4.08

Table 4: Table 3. Natural frequencies of the modified building.

Figure 19 shows different views of the fundamental mode shape of the undisturbed building. This mode shape describes predominantly bending vibrations in x-direction of the wing parallel to the street Singrienergasse. Similarly, bending vibrations in x-direction dominate the fundamental mode shape of the modified building as it can be seen from Figure 20.

The second and the third global vibration mode at natural frequencies of 4.29 Hz and 4.67 Hz, respectively, describe for both building conditions coupled bending-torsional vibrations. Exemplary, in Figure 21 and Figure 22 the second mode shape is depicted for the original and the modified building.

2.1.2.4.2 Estimation of the contribution of partition walls to the global stiffness

A simple mechanical model was utilized to determine a rough estimate of the structural stiffness of the building with and without partition walls. Thereby, the building wing parallel to the street Singrienergasse is modeled as three-story frame structure as shown in Figure 23. Columns with story-wise effective stiffness model the load-bearing walls, and rigid hinged-hinged beams describe the effect of the timber ceilings. The additional stiffness of the partition walls in the model of the original building is assigned to the columns by increasing their effective stiffness. The distributed mass of the building is concentrated to the frame corners.

The dynamic modal properties, i.e. the natural frequencies, are known from the investigation described before. Building mass and geometry of the frame model can be estimated quite accurately, and thus the stiffness of structure, which is the single unknown parameter, can be determined by system identification. In the model it is distinguished between the effective stiffness of walls with a thickness of 60 cm, and of 45 cm. The distribution of the effective stiffness is depicted in Figure 16. K60 K45

The effective stiffness is determined twice: for the original building with partition walls and for the modified building, where partition walls have been removed. As outlined in Achs (2011), the effective stiffness of the model is updated as long as the fundamental natural frequency of the building and the considered mechanical model are identical. Evaluation of the stiffness reduction ratio ΔK renders a global lateral stiffness reduction of about 57%:

$$\Delta K \approx \left(1 - \frac{K_{60,Modified}}{K_{60,Original}} \right) 100 \approx 57\%$$

Figure 19: Numerically derived second mode shape of the original building structure. a) Isometric view; b) Floor plan; c) Front view.

Figure 20: Numerically derived second mode shape of the modified building structure. a) Isometric view; b) Floor plan; c) Front view Spittelbreitengasse.

Figure 21: Numerically derived second mode shape of the modified building structure. a) Isometric view; b) Floor plan; c) Front view Spittelbreitengasse.

Figure 22: Numerically derived second mode shape of the modified building structure. a) Isometric view; b) Floor plan; c) Front view Singrienergasse; d) Front view Spittelbreitengasse.

Numerically derived second mode shape of the modified building structure. a) Isometric view; b) Floor plan; c) Front view Singrienergasse; d) Front view Spittelbreitengasse.

This large lateral stiffness reduction of the considered wing proves the substantial influence of partition walls on the seismic resistance of historic buildings. In Equation 1 $K_{60,Modified}$ denotes the effective stiffness of walls with a thickness of 60 cm of the modified building, whereas $K_{60,Original}$ denotes the effective stiffness of walls with a thickness of 60 cm of the original building.

Figure 23: (a) Section of the building structure and (b) corresponding mechanical behaviour.

2.1.2.5 Considerations

In the presented paper the influence of partition walls on the global dynamic behaviour of a historic building has been studied utilizing an experimental in-situ test procedure. This study was performed within the Austrian national research project SEISMID in an effort to identify the contribution of those non-structural elements to the seismic resistance of historic buildings. The investigation was based on the comparison of the dynamic behaviour of the building before and after the removal of the partition walls.

Therefore, two identical measurement campaigns were conducted using a heavy impact excitation and a set of accelerometers to measure the free vibration response. Thus, it was possible to quantify the impact of the partition walls on the global dynamic building behaviour. The removal of all partition walls in the investigated building wing resulted in an essential reduction of the natural frequencies, which could be led back to a degradation of the global stiffness of 57%.

2.1.3 System Identification of Wilhelminian Style Buildings in the Vienna Basin

Proofing the stability of collapse of buildings under seismic loads is mostly performed with numerical methods because of increasing non-linear effects of material response, which also causes nonlinearity regarding the stiffness and damping of structures. Any attempt to analyze the stability of buildings under conditions similar to real earthquakes would require enormous loading devices and yield undesirable damages of the buildings which then would have to be assessed. For these reasons the dynamical response of buildings is analyzed with numerical models. This is usually possible for modern buildings with a known geometry and controlled material properties. Problems emerge with old masonry buildings which have a great dispersion of material properties, accomplishments, joins etc. In this case it is mostly impossible to make sufficiently accurate assumptions, required for numerical models. For such cases it turned out, that measurements done with small amplitudes in the linear elastic range can be used for the calibration of numerical models. The calibration with this kind of data improves the accuracy of numerical models significantly even in the non-linear-elastic range.

2.1.3.1 Measurement methods

For analyzing the spectrum of single measurement points it would be sufficient to make measurements completely independent from each other. For analyzing the behavior of entire buildings it is not sufficient to focus on single measurement points. The signals have to be observed together, it is necessary to analyze their relation in space and time. For this kind of analysis the signals have to be absolutely synchronized. A possible workaround would be to work with one reference-sensor remaining on one place, whereas the other sensors can be re-positioned. With synchronized measurement devices (Brimos Wireless Recorder) it is possible to use many sensors and recording units on different places; the quality of synchronization is comparable to an assembly made with only one central recording device. The main advantage of the Brimos Wireless Recorder system is its flexibility and the lack of long cables that would be difficult to handle.

Figure 24: Acceleration sensor (left) and geophone (right).

2.1.3.2 Signal processing

2.1.3.2.1 In Time Domain

The used sensors usually take measures in three spatial directions. In this way, the translatory movement of the measured building point is documented, but in order to find out the composition of the various building movements for each single measurement point it is useful to analyze the relations between discrete sensors synchronized in time.

Figure 25: Translatory and rotatory movement.

If we assume a translatory movement, superposed with a rotatory movement around the y-axis, these movements will be recorded by the sensors drafted on Figure 25, but they cannot be interpreted immediately. If we are only interested in the vertical movement, then we can calculate the mean value of the vertical signals.

$$z_translation = \frac{z_1 + z_2}{2}$$

The rotatory movement would be equalized, if the center of rotation is exactly between both sensors. In this case, the vertical movement of the structure can be interpreted from the two combined signals. The rotatory oscillation around the y-axis causes diametrically opposed vertical oscillations (z-direction). The linearized angle of rotation (in radian) can be calculated from the given signal-combination within a defined time interval in the following way:

$$y_rotation = \frac{z_1 - z_2}{d}$$

This formula can be applied to measure rotatory oscillations around any axis that is perpendicular to the plane mounted by the line between the sensors and the vertical z-axis. These combined signals can now be treated as one signal, recorded by an imaginary sensor that would be placed exactly between the sensors and could measure vertical and rotatory movements around the y-axis.

2.1.3.2.2 In Frequency Domain

If Fourier Transformation is applied to those previously combined signals, it is possible to determine the frequencies of the vertical and rotatory movements separately. Of course, these frequencies are also visible as peaks in the FFT-diagram of the original sensors, but with signal-combination they can be assigned to the separate oscillation-components. In the following, some useful signal combinations for building-measurements and its applications will be discussed.

2.1.3.3 Signal combinations

2.1.3.3.1 Translatory movement

Normally the roof-layer of wilhelminian style buildings is the place where measurements should be made. If the roof level is in an original state (no additional flats built on top), it is mostly easy to have access. Besides, the displacements caused by oscillations are strongest in the roof level which yields very significant signals.

Figure 26: Translatory building movement in plan view.

Figure 26 shows a simplified ground sketch of a roof level. In all four corners of the building a sensor that measures the accelerations in three directions was placed. If a mean value of the signals of these four sensors for all three directions in space is built, then this combined signal equals the translatory movements of the roof level in its center. The combined signals can be seen as a virtual sensor placed exactly between the four real sensors. Thus, this is only the case, if the entire roof level behaves like a rigid structural element. In buildings built during the Wilhelminian era, this will never be the case, thus the mean vertical signals are mostly useless. In horizontal direction, the assessability is dependent on the shear rigidity of the slabs. In many cases, the shear rigidity of the slabs can be assessed by comparing the discrete signals with the mean values. In the following example, a big number of sensors were placed in the roof level of a wilhelminian style building and the mean value in horizontal direction was compared with each single signal. (ground sketch is given in Figure 26)

Figure 27: Translatory building movement in x-direction in frequency domain.

Figure 27 shows the analysis of the signals in x-direction of all sensors after FFT-analysis in frequency domain. The mean value of these signals was computed in the time domain and after that FFT – analysis was applied. In Figure 27 one can see it in bold red. A basic oscillation of 2,6 Hz in x-direction of the building is obvious in the mean value and can also be identified from each single measurement positions. But to assume, that a building from the Wilhelminian era would accomplish a rigid movement is not appropriate. Therefore the shear rigidity of the roof level is too weak. Very often, parts of a building have a „dynamic life of its own“. It is recognizable, that the part of the building along the Operngasse is oscillating at about 2,9 Hz, whereas in the part averted from the Operngasse, this 2,9 Hz oscillation is not recorded but one with 3,2 Hz. It is interesting to see that almost every sensor captures a peak at 4,8 Hz, but the mean signal does not. In this part of the building a very significant oscillation around 4,8 Hz was recorded, but the mean value does not show a peak in this frequency range. This indicates, that the oscillation is not translatory, the sensors obviously oscillate in an opposed way and equalize in the mean value. Below we want to introduce these kinds of oscillations.

2.1.3.3.2 Rotatory Movements at the Rooftop Level

Also for regarding the rotatory movement we have to assume a shear resistant plate in the roof top level.

Figure 28 shows the principle of signal combination for the rotatory part of the movement. A center of rotation is being assumed (in the case of a rectangular form it's middle point), the connecting lines to the sensor positions are drawn (in a case of a rectangular form the diagonals). Now, the two horizontal components of the sensor's signals are vectorially composed in a way that the direction is perpendicular to the connecting line and clockwise around the center. The components obtained for each sensor are averaged to an "entire rotational signal", which shows the rotatory wave forms around the vertical axis by FFT-analysis. In the case of a rectangular ground form, the position of the center of rotation is easy to find, and the sensors placed in the corners of the building are placed nearly in the same distance from the rotational center. If additional sensors are used and if they have different distances to the assumed center of rotation, the single components of the rotational signal have to be divided by the sensor's distance to the rotational center in order to describe the kinematics in a correct way. But in this case it might be a problem, that the effect of the components of those sensors are overestimated, which are close to the rotational center. In their signals there will be hardly significant components of the rotational oscillation. For this reason it is better to take only components of those sensors into consideration, whose distance to the rotational center is big and more or less equal. Then it's not necessary to regard the distance to the rotational center, because all components get the same weight. Also the dependency of the accurate position of the assumed rotational center is neglectable in this case.

Figure 28: Rotatory building movement in ground view.

Figure 29: Rotatory building movement around the vertical axis in frequency domain.

For the building shown in Figure 28, two kinds of rotatory movements were investigated. Once, four sensors placed in the corners of the buildings were used (outer corners), another time the corners close to the court in the middle (inner corners). Both rotatory signals were investigated and are shown in brown colour (Figure 29). The frequency domain analysis shows some peaks that do not coincide with peaks of other types of oscillation. The rotation at the outer corners coincides very well with the rotation at the inner corner. This can be seen as an acknowledgement of the method.

2.1.3.3 Deviatory Movements at the Roof Level

Different from translatory and rotatory wave forms; in case of deviatory movement, rigid movement caused by shear resistance of the slabs, does not have to be assumed. In opposite, in this case dynamic shear movements are made measurable. According to Figure 30, those horizontal signal components are determined, that either point to each other or point to opposite directions at the other diagonal line. By combining these components, it is possible to show a waveform that is significant for the dynamic shear movements of the entire roof floor (black dashed line in the sketch). If there is only rigid movement, this waveform must not exist and the deviation signal must theoretically equal zero. The example for this waveform is from a house from the Wilhelminian era,

which was first measured in its original state. Afterwards, the shear resistance of the existing wooden slab was improved by assembling a composite slab, that was connected to the outer walls. This didn't change the mass of the structure, but improved the shear resistance. The following figures show the change of the wave forms by assembling a composite slab.

Figure 30: Deviator building movement.

The interpretations of changes caused by the assembly of a shear resistant slab are shown in Figure 30. They show the waveform analysis with combined signals in an effective way. If there were used single sensors only, the interpretation would have been much more difficult and far more speculative.

2.1.3.3.4 Determination of the first Harmonic in the Building Cross Section

If the frequency of the first harmonic can be easily determined by applying a spectral analysis (FFT) from the first obvious peak in the low frequency range, this does not mean, that the following peaks are the following harmonics. The first harmonic in the building's cross section is shown in Figure 31 and characterized by the fact that the horizontal oscillation of the 2nd story and the roof level occur in a reverse phase. This "opposite oscillation" of the two stories can be useful for the analysis.

Figure 31: Sketch of the basic oscillation and the first harmonic in the cross section of a building

Figure 32 shows the horizontal acceleration of each floor of building in frequency domain. The basic harmonic at 2,6 Hz is easily recognizable. The amplitudes of the upper stories are higher than those of the lower stories. For determination of the first harmonic, we focus on the “opposite oscillation” of the stories OG_02 (blue line) and OG_05 (red line). Instead of comparing the phases via FFT and getting a confusing image, a more stable algorithm was developed. The opposite oscillation is characterized by the difference between the signals (OG_5 - OG_2). This difference has a maximum (thin black line L1 in diagram). If the two stories oscillate in the same phase and have a different amplitude in the basic oscillation, then the FFT of the difference-signal shows a peak, that is equal to the difference of the FFT analyses of both signals ($L2 = \text{abs}(\text{FFT}(\text{OG}_5) - \text{FFT}(\text{OG}_2))$), thin grey line in diagram). The conclusion is, that the difference of those lines (L1-L2) is an appropriate indicator for phase reverse oscillation of both stories. This line is shown in the diagram with a thick grey line. It’s first significant maximum is at 7 Hz. This is the frequency of the first harmonic.

Figure 32: Basic oscillation and first harmonic in a building’s cross section.

2.1.3.4 Dynamic measurement

2.1.3.4.1 Wave Dispersion in Elastic Body

In an elastic and isotropic medium, the compression- and shear waves propagate with different but constant velocities that are independent of the frequency of the wave and also from the structure's geometry. They depend only on the material properties. The velocity of compression waves v_p can be determined with the following formula, where E_s is the elastic modulus (with prevented lateral strain) and ρ is the density of the material.

$$v_p = \sqrt{\frac{E_s}{\rho}}$$

The shear wave velocity v_s can be calculated via the modulus of elasticity in shear G and the material density ρ in the following way.

$$v_s = \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}}$$

With the following formulas, we can transform the values into such for isotropic linear-elastic material, whereas ν is the radial strain coefficient, E is the Youngs Modulus and G is the modulus of elasticity in shear.

$$E = \frac{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}{1-\nu} \cdot E_s = 2(1-\nu) \cdot G$$

$$G = \frac{1-2\nu}{2(1-\nu)} \cdot E_s = \frac{1}{2(1+\nu)} \cdot E$$

2.1.3.4.2 Measurements of wave dispersion in masonry wall

The idea to measure the wave dispersion in masonry walls was to determine its properties in its undisturbed entity. Laboratory tests with bore cores and samples of mortar and bricks can only selectively assess the different components of masonry walls. Goal of this experiment was to capture the in situ properties of masonry walls in today's conditions after decades of loading. In order to measure the wave dispersion in masonry walls, sensors were placed along a masonry pillar in every story. The dynamic impact was realized in the top story with an impulse hammer. Hoping to be able to differentiate the shear wave from the compression wave, the sensor were placed horizontally, also the dynamic stroke was done in the horizontal direction.

Figure 33: Experiment for wave dispersion in masonry wall.

Figure 33 shows the progression of the recorded measurement signals (horizontal acceleration) according to the vertical position of the sensors in the measured masonry pillar. The dispersion velocity can be recognized by the time delay between the sensors.

$$v = \frac{19,64 \text{ m}}{0,0115 \text{ s}} = 1708 \text{ m/s}$$

Before the arrival of the wave, the signal is completely homogenous and shows no agitation. This means, that the wavefront can be assigned to the compression wave. This compression wave causes also vertical oscillations, but obviously the horizontal component is dominant. Therefore it is not possible to recognize the following shear wave. Using formulas for linear elastic, isotropic materials it is possible to estimate the material properties.

$$v_p = \sqrt{\frac{E_s}{\rho}}$$

In dependency of the radial strain coefficient, the other material parameters can be determined. Figure 34 shows the result from measurements at different pillars in the same building. Various light strokes and various strong strokes with the impulse hammer were accomplished. The nonlinearity of the material parameters is obvious. The greater the amplitudes, the lower the stiffness of the material, which yields smaller wave velocities.

	Medium impact	Strong impact	Difference
Pillar 1	1363 m/s	1315 m/s	-3,5%
Pillar 2	1546 m/s	1502 m/s	-2,9%
Pillar 3	1650 m/s	1583 m/s	-4,1%
Average	1519 m/s	1466 m/s	-3,5%

Figure 34: Different wave-velocities because of non-linear and amplitude-dependent material properties

As we have seen, it is relatively easy to measure the compression wave in a masonry pillar. The shear wave can be slightly recognized in the top story, but it is strongly damped. Because of the anisotropy of the masonry wall it would be good to be able to measure the compression wave going vertically through the pillar, as well as the shear wave, which is propagating with horizontal oscillations through the pillar in vertical direction. In this case it would be possible to determine the relevant parameters directly. No assumption for the radial strain coefficient would have to be taken. A comparison with this dynamic method for determination of material properties with conventional methods has not yet been undertaken.

2.2 Use of advanced technologies (LDV)

2.2.1 Verifications of various improvements to the vibration behavior of old masonry buildings in Vienna

At the location Fendigasse a new measurement equipment was tested. Through the usage of a Laser-Doppler-Vibrometer (LDV) it is possible to detect the velocity field of a surface like a building façade or an internal wall. The measurement points have to be in the range of the detection area of the vibrometer. The points are being measured in a timely sequence. In order to relate each point to one another, there is a reference sensor placed directly on the surface. The measurements with the Laser-Doppler-Vibrometer are especially suited for stationary conditions created by a harmonic exciter, but it is also possible to measure ambient vibrations.

Figure 35: Laser-Doppler-Vibrometer: single measurement position, electronic components, reference sensor

Figure 36: Result of a measurement of a facade, which has been excited harmonically in the 1st floor

The result of the measurement is directly after the measurement available. It is being projected on a screenshot of the integrated camera and can also be exported as a video.

2.2.1.1 Measurement of the Façade of a masonry building located in Fendigasse (Vienna)

2.2.1.1.1 Settings of the Laser-Doppler-Vibrometer (LDV)

The settings of the LDV have been kept the same for all the measurements that have been conducted during all these surveys in order to be able to compare them. All the mentioned settings are for the Laser-Doppler-Vibrometer.

The vibrometer was standing 12 meters away from the facade on the other side of the street. Because of the little distance and the huge size of the measured surface it was decided to put the vibrometer not directly in front of the facade but inclined to the wall. Between the laser head and the façade there were no obstacles so that a relatively homogenous raster of measurement points was created. Only the windows had to be avoided that the full signal can be reflected and the point can be measured.

The measurement raster was fixed at 98 points. There is the possibility to compute the average of 3 measurements for each point. This would have significantly increased the measurement time so this option was dropped. The function of measuring a point as often as needed was activated. If a point is not measured correctly it appears yellow on the screen. If this happens the vibrometer measures this particular point again but 3 times at maximum. In all the measurements there were only a few points that had to be measured again and in the end all points were measured correctly.

The measurement time added up to 20 to 29 Minutes for all the 98 points, so in average it took 30 seconds to measure one point. The measurement range was set to 10 mm/s and the frequency band from 0 to 1000 Hz.

2.2.1.1.2 Measurement Setup

The exciter "Hubert" was placed at the 4th floor of a "Gründerzeithaus" at the location Fendigasse 20.

The exciter operated at two different predefined frequencies: 4,75 Hz and 11,75 Hz. It can be operated at full weight, where the amplitudes are high and at low weight, where amplitudes are less high. Due to construction issues the exciter was operated with full weights at 4,75 Hz and without weights at 11,75 Hz.

Figure 37 shows the measurement layout. The sensors are colored in orange, the green circle shows the exciter and the blue sensor is the reference sensor at the wall (Wilcoxon). The sensor positions were chosen in order to capture the vibration behavior of the ceiling plate.

Figure 37: Measurement layout

2.2.1.1.3 Logic Procedure

The measurement of the facade divides in 4 categories:

- Reference Measurement
- Tension of the screws at the main wall
- Tension of the "Streichbalken"
- Nut inserted wooden OSB slabs in all 3 rooms

The reference measurement is necessary because one needs the original condition of the building measured. After that the different provisions will be enabled and the impact on the vibration behavior of the whole building and especially the façade will be measured.

The first provision is that the main wall is rigidly connected to the floor with threaded bolts. The main wall now has a direct connection to the floors.

The second provision is the tensions of the “Streichbalken”. The Streichbalken is a wooden beam which serves as the support between two floors. This beam is now connected to all the adjacent beams via threaded bolts.

The last provisions are the nut inserted OSB slabs in the rooms. The slabs are screwed to the floor of each room. The placement of the slabs in room where the exciter is working was realised by screwing the slabs from the room below on the ceiling.

2.2.1.2 Results

2.2.1.2.1 Results of the Chronos measurement

In this part of the report the results of the sensors, which have been placed directly on the floors in the rooms will be shown and discussed.

The first thing to do with the measured signal is to clean it from the offset. Afterwards the signal is being cut to get a most undisturbed signal. This is done because there has been construction work during the measurements and the signal should be free of such disturbances.

The signals are now resampled and a moving average of one second is being computed. The reduction interval is also set to one second. The result is a curve which represents the maximum values of the signal. Figure 38 shows the signal and the resampling with the moving average.

The moving average is then being averaged again to get the mean maximum amplitude of the sensor. One can now compare the amplitudes of the sensors and find out which of the provisions had an effect on the behavior.

Figure 38: Amplitudes of the various sensors in x – direction at an excitement-frequency of 12 Hz

One can see pretty clearly that at some of the sensors the first provision resulted in higher amplitudes. These sensors are not standing directly in the room where the exciter is placed so they are not directly connected to this floor. Because of the rigid connection of the exciter-floor to the main wall and the same connection of the floor where the sensor is placed, the vibrations are much more propagated. That is why the amplitude is rising at the first provision. After the following provisions the amplitudes are much smaller, because the distribution of the vibrations is much more homogeneous. The attachment of the slabs creates more weight on the floor, which also results in a smaller amplitude.

It can be stated that these provisions have a significant influence in the vibration behavior of the whole building, especially at the floor level, but only if all the provisions are taken together.

2.2.1.2.2 Results of the Laser-Doppler-Vibrometer

Figure 39: Vibration behavior in the reference measurement at an excitement frequency of 11,75 Hz

Figure 40: Vibration behavior in the 2nd measurement at an excitement frequency of 11,75 Hz

Figure 41: Vibration behavior in the 3rd measurement at an excitement frequency of 11,75 Hz

Figure 42: Vibration behavior in the 4th measurement at an excitement frequency of 11,75 Hz

The measurements show that the provisions have a major influence on the vibration behavior of the whole building. The reference measurement is showing a clear picture of

the amplitude distribution on the façade. The maximum can be found in the 4th floor, where the exciter was operating. If one looks at this maximum the same mechanisms as in the Chronos measurement can be found. The first provision results in a little higher amplitude on the facade, but all the further provisions result in reducing the amplitudes all over the surface because of the better distribution characteristic throughout the whole building. In the last picture it can be seen that the maximum amplitude is reduced.

2.2.1.3 Investigation of a partition wall

In Figure 43 one can see the layout of the measurement of the partition wall. This measurement was conducted in the same building as above, however not the facade but the partition wall was instrumented and measured. The vibrometer was placed as far away as possible, this is why it was placed "behind" the door opening.

The excitement of the partition wall was realised through various techniques. The first technique was a loud speaker (subwoofer) which was placed behind the wall. Various frequencies were tried out, but the most effective for such a measurement is the periodic sweep. This sweep consists of a constant periodic frequency slope from 20 Hz up to 20 kHz. This signal was repeated periodically so that every point is measured with the same frequency characteristic.

Another excitement was tested. Different balls were thrown on the back of the partition wall. In general this technique worked, but the reproducibility is very hard to realize.

Another trial was done with a medicine ball which was hung from the ceiling of the room which was below the room with the partition wall. The partition wall was going from the 3rd floor up to the roof without any interruptions of any kind. This trial was by far the best one also because of its reproducibility. The problem is that often one cannot access the room in the lower floor or that the partition wall is interrupted in some kind.

The last trial was the again the loud speaker, but this time it was placed in front of the wall in the same room where the vibrometer was standing. This setup was by far the worst and cannot be recommended in any case. The vibrations of the loud speaker interrupted the measurement in a way that the vibrometer head was moving constantly in any direction and the measurement was useless.

Figure 43: Measurement layout on the 2nd day: Measurement on the partition wall.

Figure 44: Vibration behavior of the partition wall at 8 Hz

Figure 45: Vibration behavior of the partition wall at 23,375 Hz

Figure 46: Vibration behavior of the partition wall at 31,125 Hz

Figure 47: Vibration behavior of the partition wall at 40,25 Hz

2.2.1.3.1 Numerical Analysis, Verification of the measurements

The formulas of Robert D. Blevins are being used to analytically verify the measured results:

$$f_{ij} = \frac{\lambda_{ij}^2}{2\pi a^2} \sqrt{\frac{Eh^3}{12\gamma(1-\nu^2)}}$$

For rectangular panels with various boundary conditions (free, simply supported, and clamped) there are values for λ_{ij} in the literature. λ_{ij} is needed to determine the eigenfrequency for different eigenmodes. The index i gives the number of half-waves in horizontal direction, while j stands for the number in vertical direction. The green values in Figure 50 show the measured frequencies and their corresponding mode is coded as index ij .

With the measured frequencies and theoretically determined values for λ_{ij} the quotient f_{ij}/λ_{ij} can be computed. Through this value the E-modulus can be computed for the geometric conditions and masses, which then results in the frequency.

$$E = \left(\frac{f_{ij}}{\lambda_{ij}^2} 2\pi a^2\right)^2 \frac{12\gamma(1-\nu^2)}{h^3}$$

The boundary conditions of the partition wall in the 4th floor of the building are by far not the same as the theoretical and ideal boundary conditions used to compute the analytical values. The better the E-modules fit to the real case, the more realistic are the boundary conditions.

It can be shown that the base frequency (mode 11) leads to lower E-module values than oscillation of higher orders. The reason for that could also be because of the higher amplitude in this mode and the nonlinear behavior of the material. The theoretic boundary conditions, which lead to lower standard deviations (modes 2,4,8 and 9), are more realistic compared to the real condition.

A finite element model of the rectangular panel was made using ANSYS. The different torsion springs were modeled with various stiffness. An example is shown in Figure 49.

Figure 48: Boundary Conditions for the back calculation with FEM.

Figure 49: FEM-Calculations of the different modeshapes.

The calculations using the finite element method also show that at the ground frequency the calculations and the measurements do not perfectly match.

measured frequencies

f	8,00 Hz	23,38 Hz	31,13 Hz	40,25 Hz	?	54,88 Hz	59,38 Hz	81,88 Hz
mode ij	11	21	12	31	22	32	32	41

FEM calculated frequencies

f	11,57 Hz	22,30 Hz	31,72 Hz	38,95 Hz	40,94 Hz	65,09 Hz	65,09 Hz	61,39 Hz
mode ij	11	21	12	31	22	32	32	41

relationship	1,45	0,95	1,02	0,97		1,19	1,10	0,75
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Figure 50: Comparison between the measured frequencies (green) and the FEM calculated frequencies (purple) for the various modes.

2.2.1.4 Considerations

The measurements concerning the location Fendigasse can be stated as successful. The vibrometer has been tested and various parameters have been varied. Especially in terms of excitement of the different surfaces, many useful conclusions can be drawn. Especially the measurements on the façade of the building have been very successful. The provisions represent a very efficient and cheap way to influence the vibration behavior of the building. Each provision itself can help modify it, but the most effect can be seen when all provisions are taken at the same time.

The measurements on the partition wall have shown which frequencies correspond to the different modes and how these characteristics can be measured efficiently.

2.3 Validation of the technology

2.3.1 Global Dynamic Behaviour of a Historic Residential Masonry Building at Different Stages of Demolition

In the past no particular attention was paid to the seismic assessment of historic masonry buildings in Austria. However, recent investigations have revealed that in Central Europe earthquake hazard has been underestimated considerably, and subsequently, regulations concerning the seismic hazard have been tightened. As a consequence, the seismic resistance of most of the historic masonry buildings in the Austrian capital Vienna cannot be verified anymore by common seismic analysis approaches. In recent years this problem started to attract the attention of engineers and scientists.

The structural system of historic buildings can be hardly assessed by traditional methods such as an inspection. Thus, certain structural and non-structural elements may not or must not be taken into account for prediction of the seismic resistance of an existing building. Particularly, the guideline of the municipality of Vienna for reconstruction of historic masonry buildings, MA37S (2008), regulates that non-structural partition walls with a thickness smaller than 15 cm must not be taken into account for seismic analyses. On the other hand, nonlinear structural properties of these buildings cannot be considered in the seismic assessment because experimental data for brick masonry built-in in those buildings are hardly available.

Before the guideline of the municipality of Vienna for reconstruction of historic masonry buildings, MA37S (2008), was released, the rehabilitation and modernization of historic residential masonry buildings had been common practice in Vienna. In particular, unused attics had been converted into apartments to concentrate the population in the city center. Since then, these reconstruction activities have drastically declined, mainly due to the fact that the seismic resistance of the historic masonry buildings cannot be assessed anymore with reasonable measures. This led to a huge technical debate between engineers and authorities and to an economic crisis affecting real estate firms as well as construction companies. Consequently, in 2006 the Austrian national research project SEISMID was launched. One of the main goals of this project is to develop methodologies for the assessment of the actual load-bearing capacity of historic brick masonry buildings.

It is of primary interest to quantify the contribution of non-structural walls to the seismic resistance of a building. If structure and material parameters are well defined, the outcomes of numerical studies with and without non-structural walls are set in contrast most effectively. However, this methodology may be used for newer buildings only. In historic buildings the required information about non-structural walls can be extracted only through in-situ investigations. Such investigations implicate the demolition of the non-structural partition walls, and therefore the considered building needs to be unoccupied. In an experimental investigation of reinforced concrete buildings by Hans, S., Boutin, C., Ibrahim, E. and Roussillon, P. (2005) this methodology has been already approved.

In a unique opportunity a historic brick masonry building in the city of Vienna was provided for research purposes before it was demolished. Extensive measurement campaigns were performed on this building to identify the contribution of non-structural partition walls to the global dynamic response. In the following the test procedure and results of the study on this building are presented.

2.3.1.1 Test object

The test object of the described investigation is a historic masonry building, which was located in the city centre of Vienna, Austria, at the intersection of two side streets named Spittelbreitengasse and Singrienergasse, see Figure 51. It was built about 150 years ago and has been used for housing purposes since then.

Figure 51: (a) Location of the test object within the city of Vienna, Austria; (b) Orientation of the test object to the neighbouring buildings

The three-storey building with ground floor, first floor, second floor, and an attic had two wings, which were arranged perpendicularly. Only the building wing parallel to the street Spittelbreitengasse had a basement. Its dimensions can be read from Figure 52. The object, which was constructed at the end of the 19th century, had been almost completely preserved in its original condition before the described investigations were started. The non-structural walls were almost periodically distributed on the first and second floors. On the ground floor, which was used as a restaurant, steel beams supported most of these non-structural walls.

The walls were made of brick masonry. The ceiling between the basement and the ground floor consisted of brick vaults, whereas the ceilings of the upper stories were constructed of timber beams. Steel bars connected almost all timber beams of the timber ceilings with the load bearing walls.

Figure 52: (a) Floor plan of the first and second floors; (b) Front view of the test object; (c) Section A-A representing the building wing parallel to the street Singrienergasse; (d) Section B-B representing the building wing parallel to the street Spittelbreitengasse

2.3.1.2 Test procedure and experimental set-up

2.3.1.2.1 Test Procedure

A dynamic system identification procedure based on measurement of the dynamic response was applied. Thereby, the global dynamic parameters of the test object were determined for two different conditions, i.e. for the original undisturbed building, and for a modified form of the building where a series of partition walls were removed.

At first, a series of tests was performed on the original undisturbed object. The results extracted from these in-situ measurements represent the structural properties of the building including load-bearing walls, timber ceilings, and non-structural elements such as partition walls.

Subsequently, the non-structural partition walls were removed in the building wing parallel to the street Singrienergasse, compare Figure 53, and a second test series was

conducted in the same manner as it was done in the original building condition. The material of the demolished walls was placed next to the original wall locations to leave the mass distribution almost in its original condition. The test section for recording the dynamic response was selected in this wing as shown in Figure 54. The test protocol of the performed measurements is shown in Table 5.

Figure 53: Test section; a) Original structure; b) Modified structure without non-structural partition walls.

Figure 54: Vertical distribution of the acceleration sensors in test section A-A, and experimental test set-up

Table 5: Test protocol of the conducted measurements.

Structural condition	Date	Time	No. of load impacts
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Original structure	November 10, 2008	Start 12-48-35 End 13-10-35	85
Modified structure	December 16, 2008	Start 12-43-04 End 13-05-04	100

2.3.1.2.2 Excitation

The building was excited to free vibrations by an impact of a lumped mass applied to the internal load-bearing wall above the test section. The lumped mass consisted of a bag filled with 50 kg of gravel. Figure 54 shows the point of application of the impact load.

2.3.1.2.3 Instrumentation

The induced free-vibration response of the building was recorded by capacitive accelerometers, which were connected to an A/D converter, controller and data logger. The accelerometers were directly placed and mounted on the external and internal load-bearing walls in windowsills and alcoves of the test section to capture only the global dynamic behaviour and to avoid interfering signals from local dynamic effects, see Figure 54. In vertical direction the accelerometers were distributed storey-wise on top of each other. A Cartesian system of coordinates identified the recorded acceleration response components non-ambiguously. As shown in Figure 54 denotes the vertical direction, whereas x indicates the horizontal coordinate parallel to the street Singrienergasse, and the horizontal coordinate y is parallel to the street Spittelbreitengasse.

2.3.1.2.4 Signal Processing and Data Analyses

After the measurement campaigns signal processing and data analyses were conducted in the laboratory. Thereby, the time histories' signals were transformed into the frequency domain by Fast-Fourier-Transformation, which yielded the spectral response. The signal processing was performed according to a standard evaluation method developed within the SEISMID research project, published in Achs, Adam and Wenzel (2007a and 2007b).

2.3.1.3 Results

2.3.1.3.1 Frequency Response and Mode Shapes

The horizontal components of the spectral responses in y-direction are presented in Figure 55 and Figure 56. The corresponding acceleration responses were recorded in the attic (Figure 55) and on the second floor (Figure 56), both at the internal and an external load-bearing wall. In these figures red lines correspond to the response of the original building with partition walls, and green lines refer to results of the modified building after removing the partition walls.

It can be seen that the peak responses occur at the same frequencies both for the internal and the external load-bearing wall. Thus, these walls are coupled through the timber ceilings and the roof structure, because the partition walls have been removed. In Table 6 the first and second natural frequencies $f_{1,y}$ and $f_{2,y}$, respectively, of the original building and the modified building are specified, which are identified from Figure 55 and Figure 56. The spectral responses of the modified building show a major reduction of the natural frequencies f of about 1.2 Hz when compared to the outcomes of the original building.

The identified fundamental mode shapes of the original and modified building structure are depicted in Figure 57.

Table 6: First and second natural frequencies of the original and modified building. Frequency difference Δf between the original and modified building.

Frequency	Original building	Modified building	Δf [Hz]	Δf [%]
$f_{1,y}$	3.68 Hz	2.49 Hz	1.19 Hz	32
$f_{2,y}$	4.38 Hz	3.10 Hz	1.28 Hz	29

Figure 55: Acceleration response, y-component; Left Figure: Attic, external load-bearing wall adjacent to the street. Red line: Original building. Green line: Modified building; Right Figure: Attic, internal load-bearing wall. Red line: Original building. Green line: Modified building

Figure 56: Acceleration response, y-component; Left Figure: Second floor, external load-bearing wall adjacent to the street. Red line: Original building. Green line: Modified building; Right Figure: Second floor, internal load-bearing wall. Red line: Original building. Green line: Modified building

Figure 57: (a) Normalized fundamental mode shapes; (b) Sensor positions for evaluation of the mode shapes and corresponding numbering of the modal coordinates $\phi_{i,j}$.

2.3.1.3.2 Estimation of the Global Stiffness Reduction

A simple mechanical model of the original and modified building is employed to derive degradation of stiffness due to the removal of the partition walls. Thereby, the investigated building wing is modelled as three-storey frame structure as shown in Figure 58. Since mass and geometry can be estimated very accurately, the global stiffness is the only unknown parameter. The main structural parameter, which enters the stiffness, is the bending stiffness EI of the columns. As the thickness of walls is 60 cm on the ground floor and 45 cm on the upper floor, the corresponding bending stiffnesses are referred to as EI_{60} , and EI_{45} , respectively. As outlined in Achs and Adam (2009) the stiffness of the mechanical model is determined for the original and modified building updating Young's modulus until the fundamental frequency of the building and its mechanical model are identical. Evaluation of the stiffness reduction ratio Δk

$$\Delta k \approx \left(1 - \frac{EI_{60,Modified}}{EI_{60,Original}} \right) 100 \approx 54\% (x + a)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^k a^{n-k}$$

renders a lateral stiffness reduction of about 54%. This large lateral stiffness reduction proves the substantial influence of partition walls on the seismic resistance of historic buildings. In Eqn. 4.1 $EI_{60,Modified}$ denotes the bending stiffness of walls with a thickness of 60 cm of the modified building, whereas $EI_{60,Original}$ denotes the bending stiffness of walls with a thickness of 60 cm of the original building.

Figure 58: (a) Cross section of the building structure and (b) corresponding mechanical model.

2.3.1.4 Structural damping

The fundamental modal damping coefficient ζ_1 of the original and modified structure was extracted from the decay of the free vibration response for five recorded response samples. The mean value is considered to be the representative fundamental modal damping coefficient ζ_1 . The individual damping coefficients for each response sample and the mean values are specified in Table 7. It can be seen that ζ_1 of the modified structure is 30% larger compared to ζ_1 of the original structure.

Table 7: Fundamental damping coefficients of the original and modified structure.

Sample of modal damping	Original structure	Modified structure
$\zeta_{1,1}$	3.29	4.30
$\zeta_{1,2}$	3.30	4.92
$\zeta_{1,3}$	3.34	4.10
$\zeta_{1,4}$	3.59	4.62
$\zeta_{1,5}$	3.33	4.49
Mean ζ_1	3.37	4.49

2.3.1.5 Considerations

In the presented paper the influence of partition walls on the global dynamic behaviour of a historic building has been studied utilizing an experimental in-situ test procedure. This study was performed within the Austrian national research project SEISMID in an effort to identify the contribution of those non-structural elements to the seismic resistance of historic buildings. The investigation was based on the comparison of the dynamic behaviour of the building before and after the removal of the partition walls. Therefore, two identical measurement campaigns were conducted using a heavy impact excitation and a set of accelerometers to measure the free vibration response. Thus, it

was possible to quantify the impact of the partition walls on the global dynamic building behaviour. Removal of all partition walls in the investigated building wing resulted in an essential reduction of the natural frequencies, which could be led back to a degradation of the global stiffness of 54%.

3. Contributions from EUCENTRE

3.1 *Dynamic characterization of a reinforced concrete school building in Val di Sotto (SO), Italy*

The building considered herein, depicted in Figure 59, is a public school located at the Comune di Val di Sotto (SO), in Italy. In order to fulfill energy qualification criteria recently established with Italian rules for existing buildings, the school building was inspected and a characterization of the dynamic parameters was performed. Furthermore, the experimental campaign had the purpose of using the dynamic parameters obtained by field monitoring to calibrate the numerical structural model, in order to improve its accuracy. The dynamic parameters identified during the experimental campaign, as well as the building itself, will also be used to test the methodology developed to carry out structural model updating based on field testing results, which is one of the goals of Task 15.2 of the same work package (a detailed description of the procedure can be found in Deliverable 15.2). The structure was tested using ambient vibration based procedures, as well as excitation provided by a mechanical vibrodyne.

Figure 59: School Building at Comune di Val di Sotto (SO), Italy

3.1.1 *Description of the building*

The building is a 3-storey reinforced concrete frame structure consisting of 3 parts connected by expansion joints: secondary school, entrance and elementary school. The dynamic identification measurements were carried out considering only the parts corresponding to the schools, without including the entrance. In Figure 60 the different building sections are indicated.

Figure 60: Plan view of the building

Concerning the structural members, all the vertical elements are continuous from the foundation up to the top of the building and the slabs are oriented along the longitudinal direction. The main characteristics of the slabs are described below.

- 1st level: RC slab, thickness 30cm;
- 2nd level: ribbed slab, thickness 24+4cm;
- 3rd level: ribbed slab, thickness 24+4cm.

The frame structure is connected to an external RC staircase, with wall thickness of 40cm.

3.1.2 Field monitoring equipment

In order to perform the testing procedures and obtain the experimental dynamic parameters of the building, the following instrumentation, illustrated in Figure 61 to Figure 64, was used.

- Tri-axial seismometers (geophones) type Lennartz LE3D5S;
- A/D converter NI USB-6218 8 channels, resolution 16Bit, 250kS/sec, range +10/-10Volt;
- Hardware and software for data acquisition and post-processing of the field measurements;
- Vibrodyne Valtronic 0-30Hz, 30kN force capacity;
- Analogical controller.

Figure 61: Installation and setup of the devices (vibrodyne and geophones)

Figure 62: Tri-axial seismometer placed at the roof level

Figure 63: Vibrodyne controller

Figure 64: Signal gathering

3.1.3 Data acquisition software

The data acquisition process made use of the program *Signal Express*, by National Instruments, a software application designed in a way that can be configured using most of the existing transducers. The characteristics of the time vector had to be set in order to perform a reliable analysis in the frequency domain.

3.1.4 Post-processing software

The post-processing of the field monitoring data was carried out using software made up of three components: an initial part for the data input, a second one concerning the processing of the data and the final part for the numerical and graphical output. Several filtering options can be selected in order to detect the dynamic parameters of the structural system (eigenvalues) and to disregard the non-significant eigenfrequencies.

The analysis of the results expressed in frequency domain involves the use of mathematical tools like the FFT (Fast Fourier Transform), the PSD (Power Spectrum Density), the cross-spectra and the analysis time-frequency-amplitude. With the aforementioned quantities, it is possible to obtain the required dynamic information regarding the tested building.

3.1.5 Field testing strategy

The seismometers (geophones) were placed in specific locations within the building, as schematically illustrated in Figure 65 to Figure 67, defined with a view to a reliable dynamic characterization. It is expected that in such positions, the maximum amplitude of resonance will be reached.

Figure 65: Location of the geophones at the ground level.

Figure 66: Location of the geophones at the first storey level.

Figure 67: Location of the geophones at the roof level.

The dynamic characterization was performed in two different phases. In the initial phase, the movements caused by ambient vibration were recorded and analysed whilst, in the second phase, the vibrodyne was used to generate forced vibration. The rotating masses of the vibrodyne generate sinusoidal waves: the direction of excitation was set along the three principal directions in which the structure is more likely to vibrate (i.e. longitudinal, transversal and vertical) and the frequency of the excitation was tested for several values (steps of 0.2Hz), within the range of interest.

The acquired signals were then processed to allow the estimation of the parameters of interest. The application of a low-pass filter at 50Hz was carried out in order to eliminate all the high-frequency noise that could interfere with the dynamic identification analysis

process. After filtering the signals, they were shifted from time-domain to frequency-domain representation, using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). In addition, Power Spectral Density (PSD) and all the cross-spectra were computed. These analyses, as mentioned before, were used to identify the natural frequencies of the structural system.

3.1.6 Dynamic identification measurements and data analysis

The dynamic characterization was performed considering a total of eight tri-axial seismometers, two for the ground level and three for both first storey and roof level. The first four eigenvalues were identified and the results are indicated in Table 8. Three modes are flexural whereas the fourth is torsional: the first combines both flexural deformed shapes along longitudinal (Y) and transverse (X) directions; the second is a flexural mode along the transverse (X) direction and the third is a flexural mode along the longitudinal (Y) direction.

Table 8: Field monitoring results – eigenvalues.

Mode	Description	T [s]	F [Hz]	Ω [rad/s]
1	Flexural XY	0.16667	6.000	37.69911
2	Flexural X	0.13559	7.375	46.33849
3	Flexural Y	0.12308	8.125	51.05088
4	Torsional	0.10667	9.375	58.98563

Figure 68 to Figure 73 provide examples of some of the analyses performed over the acquired data, namely the FFT, some of the cross-spectra and some diagrams frequency-time-PSD amplitude, respectively. The plots correspond to data acquired using the instrument configuration shown in Figure 65, Figure 66 and Figure 67.

Figure 68: FFT of the acquired signals – 6Hz (Flexural mode XY)

Figure 69: FFT of the acquired signals – 7.375Hz (Flexural mode X)

Figure 70: FFT of the acquired signals – 8.125Hz (Flexural mode Y)

Figure 71: FFT of the acquired signals – 9.375Hz (Torsional mode)

Figure 72: Cross-spectra (amplitude and phases) corresponding to the frequency of 6Hz (Flexural mode XY)

Figure 73: Frequency-Time-PSD Amplitude plots of channels 1

It can be observed from the different diagrams the presence of flexural eigenfrequencies, both combined (X and Y) and individual (X or Y), between 6Hz e 8,125Hz, as well as a torsional eigenfrequency of about 9,375Hz.

4. Contributions from AIT

4.1 Introduction

A unified methodology to define the assessment of seismic fragility of structures within Europe has not been developed yet. In some European areas the seismic risk was underestimated in the last years and the necessity to maintain the existing structural heritage and to adapt it to the new need of the population is a hard task. Several collapse cases of ancient masonry structures in the last two decades have increased the interest in the seismic vulnerability assessment of existing structures [Bayraktar et al.]. The real seismic vulnerability of structures built in the beginning of the previous century is not easy to assess due to the missing knowledge of the materials used to build the structures. The uncertain knowledge of the characteristics of the existing structures is increased by the degradation of the resistance of the material that is hardly predictable [Yi et al.]. In order to reduce the aleatory and epistemic uncertainty of the characteristics of the structure, some scholars used field testing data to update the numerical model of a structure ([Michel et al.], [Yi et al.]). The updated model has the characteristics more similar to the ones of the real structure, so the seismic vulnerability of that structure assessed through the updated model is more reliable than one based on the crude numerical model ([Bayraktar et al.], [Yi et al.], [Michel et al.], [Duco et al.]).

At AIT, the building vulnerability assessment will be accomplished using forced vibration methods. Our electro-dynamic exciter VICTORIA is capable of exciting frequencies between 0 and 80 Hz with a maximum input force of 35 kN. Power transmission is possible via a rod chain connecting the exciter to the building, as well as via direct ground excitation. Further information on VICTORIA and on other aspects of field testing is given in detail in NA6.

In the following, two case studies will be presented with the first one being a masonry building in Vienna and the latter one being an industrial building in Seibersdorf, Lower Austria.

The first case study is a masonry building built at the beginning of the 20th century. It is part of the residential heritage of the city of Vienna that needs to be maintained to preserve the architectonic identity of one of the biggest and most important cities of central Europe.

The building did not undergo relevant structural changes throughout the decades, but its irregular shape [EN 1998] and poor knowledge of the characteristics of its materials and of its mechanic behavior make it an interesting case of study. Furthermore, this building has wooden upper floors not fully connected to the masonry walls. These connections are very important to define the mechanical behavior of the structure [Vestroni et al.], and they are reinforced to improve the seismic resistance of the building in case it is low. The first floor is a steel-beams floor with brick slab. The authors of [Maheri et al.] stated the low seismic performance of a similar kind of floor. Finally, the last floor of the building is a special kind of floor ("Doppelbaumdecken") used only in the area of Vienna and composed by a double order of timber beams. The behavior of this kind of floor has not yet been extensively investigated in seismic vulnerability studies, so no data are available in literature to reduce the uncertainty of the knowledge of the real characteristics and behavior of the structure.

The second case study describes a reinforced concrete building. It consists of several building parts which are connected to each other by elastic building joints. The main building, which accommodates a radioactive waste combustor, has been subject to intensive field testing in order to investigate its vulnerability to earthquakes.

4.2 Case study 1: A no-reinforced masonry building in a residential district of the city of Vienna

4.2.1 General description of the building

The investigated non-reinforced bricks masonry building (Figure 74) has a ground floor, two upper floors (first floor and second floor), a mansard and an underground floor that is partially out of the ground. The mansard is covered by a timber beam roof. The floor that divides the underground floor and the ground floor is steel-beams floor with brick slab. The other three upper floors are made of wood. The last of these wooden floors is a special floor with a double order of timber-beam. The different kinds of floor transfer the excitation from a wall to the other ones in different proportions, so the dynamic behavior of the structure results quite complex. Moreover, the trapezoidal layout (Figure 75) makes the dynamic behavior of the building not easily predictable. The thickness of the brick walls is between 0.3 m and 0.75 m and their resistance characteristics are uncertain.

Figure 74: View of the building.

Figure 75: Building layout.

4.2.2 Experimental field test

The masonry building has been excited using forced vibrations. An electro-dynamic exciter (VICTORIA) was therefore linked to the building via a rod chain (Figure 76).

Figure 76: Forced excitation using VICTORIA.

The excitation was applied in the staircase between the second floor and the mansard. Several measurement sessions were carried out with the same excitation, but the positions of the sensors were changed for each session to get a larger quantity of information of the building's dynamic behavior (Figure 77).

Figure 77: Excitation and measurement points.

4.2.3 Data analysis

The measurements yielded five eigenfrequencies as given in Table 9. Via input-output modal analysis, three mode shapes could be identified (Figure 78).

Table 9: Dynamic characteristics.

Mode Number	Frequency [Hz]
1	2.64
2	4.40
3	6.09
4	8.18
5	9.44

Figure 78: Identified mode shapes.

4.2.4 Numerical analysis

A 3D Finite Element Model (FEM) of the structure has been prepared with the commercial FE code Ansys (Figure 79). This model includes all the floors (underground floor, ground floor, first and second floor and mansard), except the roof and takes into account all the openings of the structure. Both the brick masonry walls and the floors have been modeled with four-nodes shell elements. The mesh of the FEM is quite fine and regular, so the computational cost to solve the model is not low.

The steel-beams floor with masonry slab is defined as homogeneous and full connected to the masonry walls, even if in the engineering practice the bricks are considered as only dead load and not as elements carrying load. This modeling choice is due to the difficulty to define the direction of load transferring in this floor because of the irregular geometry of the building.

In the numerical model the roof has not been modeled and half of its mass has been added to the mass of the last floor and the other half mass to the mass of the masonry walls of the mansard. The wooden floors are connected to the brick load-bearing walls with unidirectional springs. These unidirectional springs have been created between each

node of the floor edge and the corresponding node of the load-bearing wall edge (Figure 80). For each couple of nodes six different springs have been defined to adjust the stiffness of the floor-wall connection for each of the six degrees of freedom. Different stiffness values have been assigned to the unidirectional springs. A higher stiffness prevents the vertical and horizontal relative displacements and the relative torsional rotation between the floor and the wall. A lower stiffness enables the relative rotation between the floor and the wall in the inflection directions. The stiffness values of these springs are uncertain, so they were chosen as parameters to update.

The masonry characteristics are uncertain due to the missing information about the materials used and its degradation throughout the time. The values of the masonry characteristics used in the initial model are taken from the EC6 [EN 1996]. The real value of the characteristics will be obtained through the model updating process.

The characteristics of the wooden floors and steel-beams floor with brick slab are also uncertain. In order to avoid an ill-conditioned problem to solve in the model updating process the characteristics of the floor will be hypothesized as certain.

The results of the first numerical simulation (Table 10 and Figure 81) show that the initial values of the masonry characteristics and the connection between the wooden floor and the load-bearing walls are not correct. This highlights the necessity of the model updating process to obtain a reliable seismic vulnerability assessment of the building.

Figure 79: FEM of the masonry building.

Figure 80: Points of connection between the masonry load-bearing walls and the wooden floors: each points indicate a couple of nodes connected.

Figure 81: First three mode shapes of the numerical model with the initial hypotheses.

Table 10: Eigenfrequencies of the numerical model with the initial hypotheses.

Mode Number	Frequency [Hz]
1	14.5
2	24.7
3	25.8
4	26.1
5	26.3

4.3 Case study 2: Industrial building in Seibersdorf, Lower Austria

4.3.1 Building description

The main building (Figure 82) with an inside radioactive waste combustor and an additional machinery complex is surrounded at all edges with building parts at different height levels. The height of the reinforced concrete structure is about 15 m and due to different foundation and mass distribution it is connected only with elastic building joints with adjacent structures.

Figure 82: The investigated building in Seibersdorf.

4.3.2 Field testing

In 2009, forced vibration tests were performed on the building using AIT's electrodynamic exciter *VICTORIA*. The exciter position is in front of the building as seen in Figure 83. Power transmission was realized via a rod chain connecting *VICTORIA* to the building at an angle of 45° (Figure 84).

Figure 85: Measurement layout: (a) 1st level (4.6m), (b) 2nd level (7.1m), (c) 3rd level (9.4m), (d) 4th level (9.6m), and (e) 5th level (12.0m).

4.3.3 Data analysis

A modal analysis was performed with the initial step having been the generation of a model grid (Figure 86). In the next step, a transfer function between the excitation point and measurement point was computed. Herein, a complex division of the respective cross spectrum by the power spectrum of excitation is performed. Resulting from this analysis, four mode shapes could be identified within the frequency range 4 to 9 Hz (Table 11).

Figure 86: Model grid.

Table 11:. Identified modes.

Mode	Frequency [Hz]	Damping (%)
1	4,6	5,1
2	5,6	6,6
3	7,5	5,6
4	8,6	2,7

4.3.4 Numerical analysis

Numerical analysis was performed using a finite-element model to compare the computed dynamic values with the measured ones. The FE model was calibrated making use of the four identified frequencies in Table 10 as well as via fine-tuning of material parameters (e.g. E-module). The model results are given in Table 12 and Figure 87.

Table 12:. Comparison of model data and measurement values.

Mode	Frequencies		Deviation in %
	Measurement	Model	
1	4,62	4,65	0,65
2	5,74	5,45	5,05
3	7,39	7,49	1,35
4	8,65	8,54	1,27

Figure 87: Calibrated FE-models (top left: 1st mode; top right: 2nd mode; bottom left: 3rd mode; bottom right: 4th mode)

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5. Contributions from AUTH

5.1 Introduction

Significant research has been done in the area of structural health monitoring, thus allowing the use of field monitoring data for the real-time seismic vulnerability assessment of existing structures. In the framework of NERA project and WP15, a methodology will be developed to account for field monitoring technologies in vulnerability analysis and loss estimation of the main elements at risk under study. In this context, AUTH will carry out validation and application studies to investigate in detail the techniques involved within the general framework of the proposed methodology. Chapter 5 has the following structure:

Subchapter 5.2 includes a general introduction to the structural health monitoring and modal analysis techniques, describing the several steps involved in experimental and operational modal analysis.

Subchapter 5.3 describes the case studies that will be covered within WP15 in order to validate the several techniques and apply the proposed methodology. The field monitoring techniques that have been conducted are described as well as the instruments (accelerograms and seismometers) used for the several experiments. Outputs from preliminary analyses performed so far are investigated. Finally the results of the preliminary numerical analyses of the case studies are presented.

In **Subchapter 5.4** an introduction in finite element model updating is attempted based on the correlation techniques between the experimental and numerical model. The general framework of the updating procedure is also described.

Finally in **Subchapter 5.5** few lines are dedicated to the description of the future work within the next period.

The AUTH research group involved in this work package is composed by the following researchers: Kyriazis Pitilakis, Anastasios Anastasiadis, Dimitris Raptakis, Dimitris Pitilakis, Sotiria Karapetrou, Grigoris Tsinidis, Evi Riga, Maria Manakou, Zafeiria Roumelioti and few more PhD students who helped during the experiments.

We acknowledge Dr Kostantia Makra and Dr Emmanuil Rovithis, as well as the technical staff from ITSAK who provided technical support and the actuator.

5.2 Structural health monitoring and modal analysis techniques

Structural health monitoring (**SHM**) can be defined as the procedure of assessing the dynamic behaviour of instrumented structures in order to observe and examine their integrity. SHM is also used as a process of implementing damage identification techniques, detecting changes in the material and/or geometric properties, boundary conditions or system connectivity of civil structures, which may affect their performance. Thus it may improve the reliability of structural systems by detecting damage before it reaches a critical state ([1], [2]). The SHM process involves the observation of a system over time based on sampling dynamic response measurements. The key part in SHM is the accurate representation of the structural properties. To determine these properties the common methods used are modal analysis techniques.

Rapid development of data acquisition and processing capabilities has given rise to major advances in the experimental operational studies and more specifically in the estimation of modal parameters of a structure. Experimental modal analysis (**EMA**) ([3], [4], [5]) is used for the derivation of the modal parameters of a linear time-invariant vibratory system and it involves the following steps (Figure 88):

- Collection of data (ambient measurements)

- Signal processing
- System identification
- Modal analysis

Figure 88: General framework of Experimental Modal Analysis

Since the EMA obtains the modal parameters from measured data (e.g. free vibration response data), one may argue that it is a path from response data to modal identification. On the other hand in case of analytical modal analysis, which is usually based on finite element modelling (**FEM**), the modal parameters are derived based on the physical properties of the system (geometry, mass, stiffness, damping) and thus it may be described as a path from spatial data to modal identification.

Traditional EMA makes use of input (excitation) and output (response) measurements to estimate the modal parameters. In the cases where it is not possible to apply the EMA, for example in the case of large structures such as high rise buildings, operational modal analysis (**OMA**), also named as output-only modal analysis may be applied. OMA utilizes only the response measurements of the structures in operational condition under ambient or natural excitation to identify the modal parameters.

System identification enables modal analyses techniques (EMA, OMA) to adopt a number of useful techniques from the modern control theory (control systems engineering). Several techniques use statistical methods to build the mathematical modelling of the dynamic systems from measured data:

- Time domain estimation methods: ARMA type procedures, stochastic realization based procedures, stochastic subspace procedures ([6], [7], [8], [9]).
- Frequency domain estimation methods: peak picking technique, frequency domain decomposition techniques ([10], [11], [12], [13]).

5.3 Presentation of the case studies

5.3.1 SDOF System. Validation Study

5.3.1.1 Construction

In the framework of the European project **SERIES** (<http://www.series.upatras.gr>), a new prototype structure (Figure 89) was built in the **EUROSEISTEST** site in order to study salient features of the SFSI mechanism and wave propagation of oscillating structures. The model structure comprises of three concrete plates, representing the foundation (one plate) and structural mass (two removable plates), connected with four

steel columns and braces between the columns on all four sides forming a totally symmetric structure. The prototype structure is founded on the free surface of the soil [14].

Forced vibration (non – permanent) and ambient vibration measurements of the SDOF prototype structure, named **EuroProteas** (<http://euroseisdb.civil.auth.gr/>), were recorded. Ambient noise data will be used among others for the system identification and the modal analysis of the SDOF system. **Europroteas** will be used as a benchmark structure for the validation of the different techniques during each individual step involved in the experimental modal analysis.

5.3.1.2 Sensor placement and technical specifications of the instruments

The forced vibration tests and the ambient noise measurements in Euroseistest were conducted by **AUTH** with the cooperation with scientists from **ITSAK**. The planned 3D configuration of the monitoring array was designed to capture the in plane and out of plane ground motion during the different tests. The soil was instrumented with 13 seismometers, 1 down-hole accelerometer and 2 SAAs, covering the two horizontal and the vertical directions. The structure was instrumented with 6 accelerometers and 2 SAAs.

Figure 89: SFSI model (EuroProteas) structure at EUROSEISTEST.

5.3.1.2.1 AUTH instruments:

7 triaxial broadband (30sec natural period) seismometers **CMG-40T** (Guralp Systems Ltd) coupled to broadband seismic recorders DAS-130-01 (Reftek). Common time was secured using GPS antennas.

CMG-40T:

Sampling frequency:

For the DAS-130-01 which are connected to the CMG-40T: 1000, 500, 250, 200, 125, 100, 50, 40, 25, 20, 10, 5, 1 sps

Amplitude range:

±10 V (20 V peak-to-peak)

Frequency range:

30 seconds – 50 Hertz (Standard)

Number of channels:

3 channels

Dimensions and weight:

for DAS-130-01 (135mm high x 185mm wide x 343mm long) / 4.5 lbs (2 kg)

for CMG-40T (154 x 207 mm) / 2.49 kg

CMG-5TD

6 digital triaxial force feedback accelerometers CMG-5 (Guralp Systems Ltd).

Sampling frequency:

4, 8, 10, 20, 40, 50, 100, 200 sps

Amplitude range:

Output sensitivity: 4 g, 2 g, 1 g, 0.5 g, 0.1 g & Peak output: ±10 V differential

Frequency range:

50 to 100 Hz

Number of channels:

3 channels

Dimensions and weight:

(176 mm x 245 mm) / 4.3 kg

SAAR (Shape Acceleration Arrays)

Two 12m-long SAAR: each contains 24 MEM sensors and has 3D sensors every 0.5m

Two 1.2m-long SAAR: each contains 8 MEM sensors and has 3D sensors every 0.15m

The sensors measure changes in gravity in 3D and record acceleration. From the accelerations, the rotation angle and displacements are also extracted. The main advantage of the SAARs is that acceleration is recorded in an array, in vertical and horizontal direction, depending on the orientation of the instrument.

Specifications of High-Bandwidth Research-Model ShapeAccelArray (SAAR)

Environmental:

- Waterproof to 100 m (water column on lowest segment).
- Operating and storage temperature: 0 to 70 oC (-40 to 85 oC optional).

Power:

- 9-12 VDC wall-mount supply (included).

Static Shape Measurements:

- Range (per segment): +/- 45 degrees.
- Absolute accuracy of tilt within 20 deg of vertical: 0.2 deg (3.4 mm/m)
- Resolution of tilt within 20 deg of vertical: 0.001 deg (0.017 mm/m).
- Azimuth error: <2 deg.
- x, y orthogonality within segments: 0.1 deg.
- Effect of temperature after compensation: <. 1 deg/degc (preliminary)

Dynamic Acceleration Measurements:

- Range: +/-2 G (x, y, or z)
- 3dB Bandwidth: 20 Hz.
- Noise floor: <2mG RMS.
- Data rate: 70 Hz or better.

5.3.1.2.2 **ITSAK instruments:**

MK-500U eccentric mass vibrator system

The forced vibrations tests were performed with an eccentric mass vibrator system provided by ITSAK. The concept behind the machinery is that two eccentric masses rotate in counter direction to each other, causing a single force in the desired direction. The amplitude of the force, as well as its direction, can be configured by the total rotating mass and operational frequency of the machinery.

MK-500U eccentric mass vibrator system owned by the Institute of Engineering Seismology and Earthquake Engineering (ITSAK) was implemented as a source of harmonic excitation imposed on the model structure. The particular mass vibrator system is a portable, uniaxial dual counter-rotating shaker that can produce a maximum horizontal force of 5 tons and can be operated from 0.1 to 20Hz. The shaker's eccentricity can be varied between 0.15kgm and 11.3kgm in various increments to produce the maximum horizontal force from 10.5Hz to 20Hz. The shaker is powered by a 2.2kW, 1200 rpm electric drive motor controlled by a Toshiba VF-S9 adjustable speed drive.

CMG-6TD

7 three-component digital (24-bit digitizer) broadband seismometer CMG-6TD

sampling frequency:

1000 – 1 samples/s

frequency range:

30 s (optional 10 s) to 100 Hz

dimensions and weight:

(154 mm x 153 mm) / 2.7 kg (entire system < 4.1 kg)

Figure 90: Structure instrumentation scheme for EuroProteas

Figure 91: Soil instrumentation scheme for EuroProteas

5.3.1.3 Experimental Modal Analysis

Ambient response measurements and data acquisition were conducted in July 2012 by the research team. **MACEC 3.2** [15] (<http://bwk.kuleuven.be/bwm/macec>), a Matlab toolbox, is applied to deal with every step of the modal analysis procedure. The collected data from the ambient tests is introduced as input in the analysis. After signal processing of the raw data, system identification techniques and modal analyses in time and

frequency domain are performed. As we have only output data in our disposal, the system identification methods, which can be used in MACEC 3.2 are the following *output-only* or *stochastic* system identification methods:

- Nonparametric PSD⁺ estimation using the correlogram or periodogram approaches;
- Reference-based data-driven stochastic subspace identification [8];
- Reference-based covariance-driven stochastic subspace identification [8];
- Operational poly-reference least squares complex frequency domain identification (pLSCF)

5.3.1.3.1 Data processing methods in frequency domain

As the data of the SDOF system are output-only data, the analysis type for FRF and/or PSD⁺ estimation should be stochastic. The pLSCF identification algorithm is a frequency-domain algorithm and therefore in the stochastic case the estimation of the matrix of **Positive Power Spectral Densities (PSD⁺)** is prerequisite. The same applies to the nonparametric technique for the Peak Picking or CMIF/FDD method. The Positive Power Spectral Density $S_{XY}^+(\omega)$ between two channels X and Y is defined as the Fourier transform of the positive lags of the cross-correlation function $r_{XY}(t)$ between these two channels [16]:

$$S_{XY}^+(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r_{XY}(t)e^{-j\omega t} u(t)dt = \int_0^{\infty} r_{XY}(t)e^{-j\omega t} dt \quad (1)$$

where $u(t)$ is the unit step function. In Figure 92, some indicative PSD⁺ are illustrated for the channels of different sensors at the top of the SDOF structure.

Figure 92: System Identification in frequency domain. Nonparametric for Peak Picking and FDD method. PSD estimation with the correlogram method

The next step is the modal analysis of the identified system models. When using the nonparametric techniques, two modal analysis methods may be selected, the Peak Picking and the Frequency Domain Decomposition (**FDD**) method. In the case of the Peak Picking method, the averaged normalized power spectral density (**ANPSD**) is computed and the modal parameters are estimated by picking the peaks in the ANPSD. In the case of FDD the singular values of the PSD matrix are computed and the modal parameters are estimated by picking the peaks in the highest singular value(s) [17]. The two modal analysis procedures are illustrated in Figure 93.

Figure 93: Modal Analysis in frequency domain. Peak Picking method – Power spectral density (left), Frequency Domain Decomposition method with the singular values corresponding to the recordings of each channel (right)

5.3.1.3.2 Data processing methods in time domain

In the case of Stochastic Subspace Identification (**SSI**), the identified model is a stochastic state-space model described by the following equations [9]:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{t+1} &= [A]x_t + w_t \\ y_t &= [C]x_t + v_t \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

, where $x_t/[A]$ and $y_t/[B]$ are the state vector/matrix and the response vector/matrix respectively at time t . The SSI algorithm aims at estimating the real system order based on the singular values computed from the QR/SV decomposition procedure (Figure 94). The modal parameters are estimated based on the stabilization diagram (Figure 95).

Figure 94: System Identification in time domain. Stochastic Subspace Identification (Singular Values)

Figure 95: Modal Analysis in time domain. Stochastic Subspace Identification (Stabilization diagram and PSD+sum)

In the following table the natural frequencies corresponding to the two first mode shapes of the SFSI model are presented based on the preliminary modal analyses performed in MACEC for the different system identification techniques. For comparison purposes, the last column is added, including the frequency values that have been computed based on the HVSr method [19] using the horizontal and vertical components of each ambient noise recording.

Table 13:. Natural frequencies corresponding to the 2 first mode shapes of the SDOF model

	PP	FDD	SSI	HVSr
f₁ (Hz)	4.4	4.4	4.2	4.5-5
f₂ (Hz)	9.5	9.5	9.6	9.5-10

5.3.1.4 Numerical model (Finite Element Model)

Preliminary numerical analyses have been performed in order to investigate the dynamic response of SFSI model. The main properties of the structural model and the soil profile are described in Table 14.

Table 14: Soil and structure properties for the preliminary numerical simulation of the SDOF model

Soil	Structure	Foundation slab – roof slabs
$V_{s1} = 140\text{m/sec}$ $H_1 = 4\text{m}$ $V_{s2} = 230\text{m/sec}$ $H_2 = 16\text{m}$ $\rho_s = 2\text{t/m}^3$ $G_{s1} = 39200\text{KPa}$ $G_{s2} = 105800\text{KPa}$ $\nu = 0.3$ $\zeta = 0.05$ (Rayleigh)	$H_{str.} = 4\text{m}$ Columns: QHS 150x10 X-braces: L 100x10 Steel $E = 210\text{GPa}$ $\nu = 0.3$ $\zeta = 0.05$ (Rayleigh)	$h_{sl.} = 0.4\text{m}$ Concrete $E = 28\text{GPa}$ $\nu = 0.2$ $2B = 3\text{m}$ $\zeta = 0.05$ (Rayleigh) $m = 18\text{t}$

The analyses are conducted in ABAQUS and ANSYS [14]. Various configurations of the coupled system were parametrically examined including:

- A SDOF structure resting on a two-layer soil (Figure 96a) modeling Euroseistest site profile until the level of -20m.
- A detailed model of the structure on a two-layer soil (Figure 96b) modeling Euroseistest site profile until the level of -20m.
- A SDOF structure founded on 8-layer detailed model of the foundation soil (Figure 96c) following [20]. Shear wave propagation velocity profiles corresponding to the 2-layer and the 8-layer system are compared in Figure 96d.

Figure 96: 3D FE models of the coupled SFSI system (a) SDOF on a two-layered foundation soil (b) Detailed model of the structure on a two-layered soil (c) SDOF model on a detailed 8-layer model of the foundation soil shown in (d)

Proper structural and mass characteristics are assigned to the numerical models to obtain also the fixed-base period of the structure. 8-noded brick elements were used for the soil meshing. The length of each element was defined according to the anticipated wavelength of shear waves propagating in the soil. The total mesh size was extended to a horizontal distance of $L = 45\text{m}$ to prevent spurious wave reflections at the boundaries, corresponding to a normalized model dimension (L/B) at 15. The footing was modeled with stiff brick elements with concrete's elastic properties. Perfect bonding between footing and soil is considered.

The fundamental frequency of the SSI system f_{SSI} based on the FE models is computed for both ANSYS and ABAQUS approximately at **5.7Hz**. A substantial influence of foundation compliance on the vibrational characteristics of the structure, leading to approximately 40% decrease of the fundamental natural frequency of the system with respect to the fixed-base case ($f_{\text{str.fixed}}=9.2\text{Hz}$). The difference in the computed fundamental frequency compared to the previous experimental ones is under investigation, but could be probably attributed to the low depth of the soil profile beneath the structure, that was taken into account in the numerical analyses.

5.3.2 AHEPA hospital. Application Study

The AHEPA general hospital in Thessaloniki is one of the largest hospitals in northern Greece. It is a major teaching and research hospital and part of the National Healthcare System of Greece. The hospital complex consists of 40 buildings of various functions and typologies, 2 electrical substations, a gas distribution network and an underground water supply system. Many of these buildings were built before 1985 and are classified as low seismic code design structures. In case of the emergency its central location in the city of Thessaloniki makes it one of the most important medical care centers for an efficient crisis management.

Figure 97: Map of the AHEPA hospital complex with the target building

The hospital complex is illustrated in the map of Figure 97. The target building, marked with the red circle, consists of two adjacent tall buildings (Figure 97) divided statically with a structural joint allowing though their interaction in case of dynamic loading. The

building hosts both administration and hospitalization activities. It was constructed in 1971 and is a seven-storey reinforced concrete structure with basement. Low code level has been used for its seismic design. The force resisting mechanism consists of reinforced concrete moment frames. The building foundation consists of footings without connecting beams combined partially with a raft foundation. Static drawings for this building are available.

Figure 98: Plan view and cross-section of the target building

Figure 99: Photos of the target building

5.3.2.1 Permanent instrumentation

In the framework of the REAKT EU project (<http://www.reaktproject.eu/>) and with the cooperation of GFZ (<http://www.gfz-potsdam.de>), the permanent instrumentation will be used for the development and application of an Early Earthquake Warning algorithm as well as for the structural health monitoring of the building. SOSEWIN network [21] is applied for the permanent instrumentation of the AHEPA building.

The configuration plan of the instruments, as illustrated in Figure 100 and Figure 101, consists of 13 accelerometers, one sensor at the basement, one at the 1st floor, 4 at the middle and 7 at the top floor (Figure 100).

Figure 100: Out plan of the SOSEWIN sensors

Figure 101: 3D view of the building with the configuration and orientation of the SOSEWIN sensors.

The various sensors communicate with each other via a wireless system that exploits the routing concept. Two more sensors are installed in the laboratory of Geotechnical Engineering in the Dept. of Civil Engineering of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki which act as gateways, collecting the data streams from the other sensors and transferring them to the Seiscomp3 server (<http://www.seiscomp3.org/>) which is installed also in the University, through the seedlink real-time data acquisition protocol (Figure 102).

Figure 102: Location of the gateway nodes in relation to the target building.

In the following table the technical specifications of the various components that make up the sensing nodes used in SOSEWIN are summarized.

Table 15: Technical specifications of the SOSEWIN network [21]

Accelerometers (MEMS ADXL203 chip)	
Bandwidth	25 Hz (up to 2.5 kHz)
Sensitivity	1 V/g
Measurement range	± 1.7 g
Output noise	0.5 mg (rms) at 20 Hz
Digitizer board	
Number of channels	4
AD converter resolution/effective resolution	24/19 bits
Input voltage range	± 5V
Input impedance	50kΩ
Bit weight	0.6 μV
Sample rate	50 to 400 sps, standard is 100 sps
Signal bandwidth (-3dB)	20 Hz
Stop bandwidth attenuation	> 80dB at 80 Hz or higher
Analogue anti-alias filter	2 nd -order 30-Hz low-pass Butterworth
Timing	GPS NMEA messages and PPS
Timing accuracy	± 5 msec at 100 sps
Digital output	USB (2x virtual com-port, 115 kBaud data/4800 baud GPS)
Temperature range	-20° to +70°C
Power supply	+5V (USB) or 9 to 18 V (on board DC/DC converter)
Power consumption	50 mA at 5V plus 70mA at 5 V for the GPS module
WRAP board	
CPU	233 MHz AMD Geode SC1100 (486er core)
DRAM (dynamic random access memory)	128 MB SDRAM (synchronous dynamic random access memory)
Operating system	
Storage	CompactFlash card, currently 2 GB
Power consumption	3 to 5 W at 12 V DC (excluding miniPCI cards)
Safety features	Watchdog timer built into the CPU, LM77 thermal monitors
User interface	3 front leds, console I/O redirected to serial port
Possible expansions	LPC bus for adding more serial ports, ISA style I/O, GPIO and I ² C bus
Connectivity	1 Ethernet channel (National DP83816), 2 miniPCI slots, 1 serial port
BIOS	tinyBIOS version 1.11

5.3.2.2 Thessaloniki Earthquake 12 May 2012, 22:48:11 (GMT), Magnitude Mw=4.0

The permanent instrumentation has already been used to record real seismic events, as for example in the case of Thessaloniki Earthquake in 12th of May with a magnitude Mw=4.

Figure 103: Thessaloniki Earthquake information taken from GFZ (<http://www.gfz-potsdam.de>) (left) and EMSC (<http://www.emsc-csem.org>) (right)

The recorded data have been processed by GFZ in a preliminary level as presented in the following figures. Impulse Response Functions (**IRF**) are computed for the recorded accelerograms. IRF matrices may be used in system identification techniques in deterministic system realization schemes proposed by several authors ([22], [23], [24]).

Figure 104: Earthquake recordings at the top and 4th floor of the hospital building (1g ~2.2 10⁶ counts)

Figure 105: Impulse Response Functions for the top and 4th floor recordings

5.3.2.3 Ambient noise measurements

Ambient noise measurements were also recorded for the system identification of the hospital building under study. The ambient noise survey was conducted in May 2012 in cooperation with GFZ (<http://www.gfz-potsdam.de>). Eleven seismometers in total were installed, two at the basement, two the 4th floor and 6 at the roof (Figure 106). One instrument was used as a reference point and was installed at the ground. The monitoring ran for some hours during one night. In Figure 106 and Figure 107 the location of the seismometers is illustrated.

Figure 106: Location of the seismometers for the ambient noise measurements.

Figure 107: 3D view of the building with the configuration and orientation of the sensors.

Continuously a description of the technical specifications of the instruments used for the ambient noise measurements is presented.

AUTH instruments:

Triaxial broadband (30sec natural period) seismometers **CMG-40T** (Guralp Systems Ltd) coupled to broadband seismic recorders DAS-130-01 (Reftek). Common time was secured using GPS antennas.

CMG-40T:

Sampling frequency:

For the DAS-130-01 which are connected to the CMG-40T: 1000, 500, 250, 200, 125, 100, 50, 40, 25, 20, 10, 5, 1 sps

Amplitude range:

±10 V (20 V peak-to-peak)

Frequency range:

30 seconds – 50 Hertz (Standard)

Number of channels:

3 channels

Dimensions and weight

for DAS-130-01 (135mm high x 185mm wide x 343mm long) / 4.5 lbs (2 kg)

for CMG-40T (154 x 207 mm) / 2.49 kg

GFZ instruments:

EDL (Earth Data Logger) digitizers and **Mark L-4C-3D** geophones (1Hz passive geophone)

The version with 3 channels was used, with pre-amplifier gain=1, sampling rate=100 Hz.

Mark L-4C-3D:

- Seismometer 210Units: 3 components, 1Hz, 5500 Ohms coil resistance
- **Mechanical parameters:** Sensor 3 orthogonal geophones
- **Signal output:**
 - Generator constant 270Vs/m
 - Output 180Vs/m (due to built – in damping)
 - Response: ground velocity from 1 Hz to >100 Hz
 - Damping: set to 0.7 by built – in resistor
- **Physical parameters:**
 - Weight: 13kg
 - Operating temperatures: -20 to +60°C

In the following figures some of the measured processed data are presented, in particular the amplitude spectrum with respect to the frequency of the three components of a sensor located at the top of the building.

Figure 108: Amplitude spectrum with respect to the frequency for the three components of sensor 9853 at the top of the building.

5.3.2.4 Numerical Model (Finite Element Model)

Preliminary finite element modelling of the instrumented building is in progress using the FE code SAP2000. For this purpose the available static drawings of the building are used. The provisions of the design code corresponding to the period of design and construction of the building is also taken into consideration to define structural parameters in cooperation with the Technical Service of the AHEPA hospital.

Initially the two adjacent buildings are modelled and analyzed separately (Figure 109). Continuously based on appropriate simulation of the structural joint the two parts of the building will be included in the same model.

Figure 109: Preliminary FE modelling of the 1st part of the hospital building in SAP2000

5.4 Finite Element Model Updating

The experimental results are considered to represent the actual dynamic behaviour of the structure and for this reason it is common practice to “correct” (or update) the finite element model based on these results in case of discrepancies [3].

The finite element model updating procedure will be applied within the NERA project to correlate the FE model with the experimental results from the field measurements with final aim the seismic vulnerability assessment corresponding to the actual state of the structure. The field testing methodology contributes in reducing the epistemic as well as aleatory uncertainties in the risk assessment procedure. The general steps involved in the “real-time” vulnerability assessment methodology can be summarized in the following scheme of Figure 110.

Figure 110: Seismic vulnerability assessment based on field measurements

The aim of the FE model updating procedure is to define the “best” model within a number of simulated models based on the most representative natural frequencies and mode shapes of the actual structural system ([25], [26],[27]).

The correlation between the experimental results and the finite element model may be achieved through the appropriate modifications in the structural properties (mass, stiffness, damping). This updating procedure is based on sensitivity analyses, identifying those physical parameters of the FE model that affect the most the dynamic behaviour. Monte Carlo method may be used for the repeated random sampling of the structural or physical parameters involved in the FE model updating process.

Accuracy level of the correlation between the experimental and numerical mode shapes may be measured based on the *Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC)* [28] which is defined as:

$$MAC_i = \left[\frac{(\phi_e^T \phi_a)^2}{(\phi_e^T \phi_e)(\phi_a^T \phi_a)} \right] \quad (3)$$

Where ϕ_a represents the i -th analytical mode shape and ϕ_e the corresponding i -th experimental mode shape.

The general framework of the FE updating methodology is described in the diagram of Figure 111.

Figure 111: General framework of the FE model updating procedure

5.5 Future work plans

For the next period the following work tasks have been planned:

AHEPA hospital: The ambient noise measurements will be repeated within the next period completing the same time the numerical analyses of the hospital building.

Europroteas model: The experimental modal as well as the numerical analyses will be finalized.

System identification techniques for the experimental/output modal analysis as well as the proposed finite element updating methodology will be validated based on the Europroteas model and finally applied in the hospital building.

Methodology for the seismic vulnerability assessment using field tests: The methodology will be further developed and validated with the experimental data.

6. Contributions from KU Leuven

6.1 *Optimal sensor placement in vibration based monitoring*

Test design is crucial for a successful test campaign. First, the whole structure has to be conceptualized: the structural current state has to be clearly understood. Potential failure mechanisms have to be defined in close communication with the owner and the operator of the structures (buildings, lifelines, etc.). As much as possible, relevant information should be collected from site visits, as-built drawings, design documents as well as, in some cases, geometry through measurement and photogrammetry. Based on that a pre-test model will be developed (also commonly referred to as *a priori* modelling). In the end, test design will help to build a feasible measurement grid with the choice for location of reference sensors and where to excite the structure in case of a force vibration test.

After conceptualization process and a pre-test model, a fundamental task is to choose a grid specifying the degrees-of-freedom (DOFs) to be measured. It is neither impossible nor necessary to measure all DOFs of a real civil engineering structure on site. The purpose is to acquire enough information to identify and derive the dynamic signature of a structure. Until now, it is only possible to measure the translational movements, whereas to measure the rotational ones are still impractical. Therefore, designing a proper measurement grid is very important. The measurement grid has to be dense enough to have a good resolution for the identified mode shapes. A coarse measurement grid might lead to spatial aliasing that may cause a wrong interpretation of higher mode shapes. A natural design of the measurement grid is based on the structural type and also practical considerations. For instance with a high rise building, it is good to attach one sensor on each floor, as conventional design is often in favour of a rigid floor and flexible column. In this situation we confine our investigation to the weakest direction vulnerable. The measurement grid could be changed if we consider also vibrations in the other two directions as well as torsional modes. With the rigid floor assumption hold we need at least three sensors on each floor to characterize the dynamic behaviour. Figure 112 shows six instrumentation positioning models for acceleration measurements of a seven-storey building.

Figure 112: Six models for the instrumentation of a building [Huang and Shakal, 2001]: a) base or reference free-field only; b) base and roof; c) reference free-field, base and roof; d) base, mid-height and roof; e) multi-level lateral motion and roof only torsion; f) multi-level lateral and torsional motions.

6.1.1 General measurement design for buildings

The strategy to design a measurement grid and to rove sensors for buildings might follow a two-step approach: (i) to measure the (horizontal) dynamic behaviour of the global structure, i.e. the columns and associated beams that form the principal structural framing of the building; (ii) to measure the (vertical) vibration of the floors. The former is somewhat similar to vibration measurement of a bridge but in the lateral directions. Therefore this part refers to floor vibration test only. Further information can be found in two guidelines [Pavic et al. 2008a,b and Smith et al., 2009]. The aim of a vibration test is to have as much information content as possible for the purpose of modal identification. On the other hand we have to confront with the fact that there is always limited time and resources notwithstanding other issues facing a field test such as safety procedure and accessibility.

For a conventional floor with primary and secondary beams as in Figure 113, the measurement grid is often based on the layout of the beams. For example, if the primary beams are considered very stiff compared to the secondary beams, the measurement line strategy can be adopted in which the measurement lines are based on the secondary beams and rove along the primary beams.

For an unconventional floor, a pre-test model is required in order to conceptualize the dynamic behaviour. Then, reference sensor locations and a fine enough grid to capture modes in the frequency range of interest will be designed.

Figure 113: Typical assumption for a beam column system.

6.1.2 Optimal sensor for structural identification

6.1.2.1 Problem descriptions

For a linear structural model, arising from the discretization of continuous domain using e.g. the finite element (FE) method, the equation of motion can be expressed by the following system of ordinary differential equations in a matrix form:

$$M\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + C\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + K\mathbf{u}(t) = \Gamma\mathbf{z}(t)$$

Where M , C , K are the mass, damping and stiffness matrices, respectively. $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is the displacement vector. $\mathbf{z}(t)$ is the vector of input forces and Γ is the force input selection matrix and, therefore, $\Gamma\mathbf{z}(t)$ forms the vector of nodal forces.

Although the above physical model is a good presentation of a vibrating structure, it is not directly useful in an experimental context. The equation of motion is continuous in time, whereas measurement data are available as discrete time samples. Therefore, it is natural to convert this model to discrete time response vectors as $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_k, \dot{\mathbf{u}}_k, \mathbf{u}_k$ with $k = \{1, \dots, n\}$ denotes the time index at time $k\Delta t$ and n is the number of samples, generalized by \mathbf{x}_k and can be computed at all n_d DOFs from the model. Strain can also be readily adapted into the formulation.

The goal of modal analysis is to find the modal coordinate vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ for the m modes in a frequency range of interest. By definition the response vector \mathbf{x} is given as:

$$\mathbf{x} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}\boldsymbol{\theta}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Phi}$ is the mode shape matrix for m contributing modes.

The objective of a modal identification test is to design a sensor configuration that provides the most information in order to estimate the modal coordinate parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ from measured data. Let $D = \{\mathbf{y}_k; k = 1, \dots, n\}$ be the measured sampled response time history data, where \mathbf{y}_k refer to the output data. The measurable response quantities are assumed to be either absolute accelerations, or displacements or velocities. The measured response and the model response prediction at time instant $k\Delta t$ satisfy the prediction error equation:

$$\mathbf{y}_k = L[\mathbf{x}_k(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + e_k(\boldsymbol{\theta})]$$

where e_k is the prediction error due to both modelling inaccuracy and measurement error. The matrix L is the observation matrix that maps the model DOFs to the measured DOFs. Therefore, it defines the location of sensors in the structure.

Using a Bayesian identification methodology [Beck and Katafygiotis, 1998; Katafygiotis and Lam, 1998], the uncertainties in the values of the identified parameters θ are quantified by probability density functions (PDF) that are obtained using the dynamic test data set D and the probability model for the prediction error $e_k(\theta)$. The prediction error vector at time $k\Delta t$ is modelled as a Gaussian random vector with zero mean and covariance Σ_t , which is assumed independent of time. Applying Bayes's theorem, the updating PDF $p(\theta|\Sigma_t, D)$ of the set of structural model parameters θ given the measured data D and the prediction error Σ_t takes the form:

$$p(\theta | \Sigma_t, D) = c \frac{1}{(\sqrt{2\pi})^n \sqrt{\det \Sigma_t}} \exp \left[-\frac{nn_0}{2} J(\theta; \Sigma_t, D) \right] \pi(\theta)$$

where

$$J(\theta; \Sigma_t, D) = \frac{1}{nn_0} \sum_{k=1}^n [\mathbf{y}_k - L\mathbf{x}_k(\theta)]^T \Sigma_t^{-1} [\mathbf{y}_k - L\mathbf{x}_k(\theta)]$$

represents the measure of fit between the measured and the calculated model response time histories; function $\pi(\theta)$ is the prior distribution for the parameters set θ ; and c is a normalizing constant chosen such that the PDF in that equation integrates to unity.

6.1.2.2 Prediction error correlation model

The prediction error e_k consists of measurement error and model error. It is natural to assume measurement error and model error independent and therefore their covariance is also independent. The covariance of the total prediction error is given in the form:

$$\Sigma_t = \bar{\Sigma} + \Sigma$$

where $\bar{\Sigma}$ and Σ are the covariance matrices of the measurement and model errors, respectively.

In a modal test design values for individual covariance matrices have to be assumed. Such assumptions are often based on the nature of the problem analysed. Measurement error may not depend on sensor location so that $\bar{\Sigma}$ takes the diagonal form $\bar{\Sigma} = \sigma^2 I$, where I is the identity matrix. However, a certain degree of correlation should be expected for the model error between two neighbouring locations. This correlation can be taken into account by selecting a non-diagonal covariance matrix Σ . The correlation Σ_{ij} between the prediction errors at DOFs i and j in the model is given by:

$$\Sigma_{ij} = \sqrt{\Sigma_{ii}\Sigma_{jj}} R(\delta_{ij})$$

that accounts for the spatial distance δ_{ij} between DOFs i and j , where $R(\delta_{ij})$ is a (decreasing) correlation function satisfying $R(0) = 1$. In fact, the covariance matrix should be consistent with the actual errors and correlations as observed from measurements. However, in a pre-test design stage such information is not available to guide the selection of the correlation between prediction errors. Instead a correlation function should be postulated to proceed with the design of the optimal sensor locations. Without loss of generality the following relation is assumed:

$$R(\delta) = \exp\left(-\frac{\delta}{\lambda}\right)$$

where λ is a measure of the spatial correlation length.

6.1.2.3 The information entropy and its asymptotic approximation

The updated PDF $p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \Sigma, D)$ represents the uncertainty in the structural model parameter values based on the information contained in the measured data. The information entropy is defined in [Papadimitriou et al., 2000]:

$$h(L; | \Sigma, D) = - \int \ln p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \Sigma, D) p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \Sigma, D) d\boldsymbol{\theta}$$

to provide a unique scalar measure of uncertainty in the estimate of the structural parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The information entropy depends on the available acquired data from the sensor configuration L .

An approximation of the information entropy is useful as in the experimental design stage neither sensor configuration nor measurement data are yet available. The following approximation has been given in [Papadimitriou, 2004], which is based on the Laplace method of asymptotic approximation:

$$h(L; \Sigma, D) \sim H(L; \boldsymbol{\theta}_0, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{2} n_0 \ln(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \ln[\det Q(L; \boldsymbol{\theta}_0, \Sigma)]$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ is the optimal value of the parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ that minimizes the measure of fit $J(\boldsymbol{\theta}; L, D)$; and $\det(L; \boldsymbol{\theta}_0, \Sigma)$ is a semi-positive definite matrix defined as $nn_0 \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^T J(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \Sigma, D)$ and asymptotically approximated by:

$$Q(L; \boldsymbol{\theta}_0, \Sigma) \equiv Q(L, \Sigma) = (L\Phi)^T (L\Sigma L^T)^{-1} (L\Phi)$$

which is independent on the nominal parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ chosen.

It is noted that this asymptotic approximation is valid for large number of data ($nn_0 \rightarrow \infty$). In the initial stage of designing a modal experiment, the data and consequently the optimal sensor configuration as well as the form of the prediction error covariance matrix are not available. In practice, useful designs can be obtained by taking some nominal values $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$ and Σ .

6.1.2.4 Formulation as a discrete-valued optimization problem

The purpose of optimal sensor design in a modal test is to seek possible locations in the structure such that the resulting measured data are most informative in estimating the modal parameters. Since the information entropy gives the amount of useful information contained in the measured data, the optimal sensor configuration is selected as the one that minimizes the information entropy. That is:

$$L_{\text{optimal}} = \arg \min_L H(L; \boldsymbol{\theta}_0, \Sigma)$$

Based on this formulation, two heuristic sequential sensor placement (SSP) algorithms, the forward (FSSP) and the backward (BSSP), were proposed for solving the optimal sensor configuration problem [Papadimitriou, 2004; Papadimitriou and Lombaert, 2012].

According to FSSP, the algorithm initiates with no sensor. The positions of sensors are computed sequentially by placing one sensor at a time in the structure at a position that results in the highest reduction in information entropy. Specifically, at each iteration, combinations with one additional sensor to the previous configuration are considered, and the information entropy of all new sensor configurations are evaluated. The selected new sensor placement is the one that minimizes the information entropy values. On the contrary, the BSSP algorithm is used in an inverse order, starting with sensors placed at all measurable DOFs of the structure and removing successively one sensor at a time from the position that results in the smallest increase in the information entropy.

The computations involved in the SSP algorithms are an infinitesimal fraction of the ones involved in the exhaustive search method and can be done in realistic time. Other heuristic search methods for solving this discrete optimization problem, such as genetic algorithm (GA), may require significantly more computational effort than the SSP algorithms. Although the SSP algorithms are not guaranteed to give the optimal solution, they were found to be effective and computationally attractive alternatives to the GAs in the optimal sensor location problem.

6.1.2.5 Minimum number of sensors and information entropy analysis

The information matrix Q is non-singular only if the numbers of sensors, n_0 , is at least equal to the number of contributing modes m (in the modal coordinate vector θ). If the information matrix is singular, then its determinant will be zero for any sensor configuration, thus, the problem has no solution. Physically, it means that the information content in the intended measurement is not sufficient to estimate all the parameters of the model simultaneously. The problem is critical for the FSSP algorithm where it initiates with no sensor. The configuration when the numbers of sensor less than the contributing modes m will cumulatively affect the optimal sensor configuration at later iterations. It is proposed to use an alternative by maximizing the product of the non-zero eigenvalues in the information matrix.

The following discussion, proved in [Papadimitriou and Lombaert, 2012], is useful particularly for design setups for the modal identification test. The information entropy is a measure of the uncertainty on measured data for which model parameters to be estimated. The more sensors added will have the effect of providing more information about the system parameters and thus reducing the uncertainties in the parameter estimate. Moreover, the minimum for m sensors are decreasing functions of the number of sensors m , independent of the correlation model assumed for the prediction error. In other words, the more sensors to use, if optimally distributed, the information quality will increase but the gain is a diminishing function of the number of sensors. This proposition is in fact very useful in determining an adequate number of fixed reference sensors, leaving others as roving sensors to speed up the test. As often the case in vibration based testing of civil engineering structures, there are only limited instrumentation resources.

If a structure is implemented with s sensors in a configuration L_s . Let λ be the correlation length and λ is sufficiently small compared to the minimum distance between any two sensors in L_s . The information entropy for the sensor configuration L_{s+1} with an additional sensor is a decreasing function of the shortest distance of the new sensor from the other existing sensors. This implies that locations further away from existing sensors have a higher information content. Therefore, the spatial correlation of the prediction error tends to shift a sensor away from existing sensor locations. Over a distance larger than the characteristic length, the spatial change of the response sensitivity will eventually control how far away the new sensor is placed from the existing ones.

6.1.3 Test design for a building in Turkey with optimal sensor location

North-west Turkey has been hit by two destructive earthquakes in 1999. A general review of these earthquakes can be found in [Bakir and Boduroglu, 2002]. After that, just over 750,000 buildings in the region to the north of the Sea of Marmara in Turkey were investigated for deriving an earthquake loss model for the particular area due to the high levels of hazard and exposure in this region. The buildings have been separated into 'good' and 'poor' classes. This classification was based on the considerations of the construction year, evidence of poor construction quality derived from construction type, and the presence of a weak ground floor.

The building considered is located in Bolu and is a moment resisting reinforced concrete frame system that represents a typical residential building in the Marmara region isolated from other buildings at both sides with a beam side-sway failure mechanism. The building is chosen such that its geometrical, material and limit state properties are within the confidence intervals of the 'good' building classification for the above-mentioned study. The building considered is a moment resisting reinforced concrete frame system

The drawings of the building are taken from the curated depository of Turkish building data on the Kocaeli Golcuk and Duzce Bolu earthquakes of 1999 maintained by a consortium of several universities (Bogazici University, University of Kansas, University of Michigan, Middle East Technical University, University of Minnesota, Notre Dame University, Purdue University and the University of Texas at Austin) [<http://www.anatolianquake.org/>]. The building is a four storey structure with three bays. The floor system is flat slab with beams. The building has a typical storey height of 2.85m and considered as regular in elevation. The dimensions of the columns are typically 0.5m x 0.25m or 0.5m x 0.25m and the dimensions of the beams are 0.25m x 0.5m. The concrete design strength is 16 MPa. The building does not have a basement and is fixed at the foundations. The building was under construction when the 1999 Mw = 7.4 Kocaeli and Mw = 7.1 Duzce earthquakes hit the region. After the 1999 earthquakes, it is reported that the reinforced concrete frame was moderately damaged.

6.1.3.1 FE model of the reinforced concrete frame

The structure is modelled by the FE package program ANSYS [Ansys, 2011] and is idealized as a two-dimensional frame taking into account the weights of the slabs in the transverse direction in the FE model (Figure 114). Eight beam elements per beams and six beam elements for columns are generated for the FE model. In the first stage, in order to obtain the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the system, modal analysis is carried out by using the Block Lanczos extraction method with a sparse matrix solver. The mode shapes are normalized to unity. This stage of the analysis gives the structure's modal properties. The first six mode shapes of the frame are shown in Figure 115 - Figure 117.

Figure 114: The idealized three-story reinforced concrete frame.

Figure 116: The third and the fourth vibration mode of the reinforced concrete frame.

Figure 117: The fifth and the sixth vibration mode of the reinforced concrete frame.

Figure 118: The location of the response points of the reinforced concrete frame [Bakir et al., 2008].

6.1.3.2 Optimal sensor location design

A typical sensor location is given in Figure 118. There are 16 measurement points, in which four are to measure transverse vibration and the rest are located at the midpoint of each beam. This sensor arrangement was based on experience and intuition. The beam-floor system is assumed to be relatively strong compared to the flexural displacement of the column. Therefore, measuring the lateral vibration in one column are enough to characterize the whole vibration. Whereas, for each span, measuring only at mid-point is an absolute minimum. From this configuration, it is easy to conclude that it will be difficult to characterize vertical vibration for certain modes. This measurement grid is quite sufficient to characterize the dynamic properties of this particular structure. However, for bigger and more complicated structures, we might need many more measuring locations. The optimal sensor location design is helpful to decide sufficient

number of sensors and their respective location, especially in case there is not enough time, instrumentation and other constraints.

The search for optimal locations is based on a pre-defined potential measurable positions. These are chosen coincident with the nodal points of the finite element model. The effect of spatial correlated prediction errors is taken into account. Since the measurable locations form a relatively dense grid, it can be already anticipated that taking into account correlation between sensors is important to maximize the quality of the data obtained from the selected subset of sensors. In the next computation, it is assumed that the prediction errors are mutually correlated depending their relative difference with correlation function. The correlation length is chosen as $\lambda = 4d = 2 \text{ m}$, with d is the minimum distance between two consecutive measurable points of the grid in the longitudinal direction. The actual correlation length in the phase of optimal sensor location is unknown and depends on the measurement as well as model error which is expected distributing along the structure in the present case. The prediction errors between the vertical and the lateral accelerations are assumed to be uncorrelated. This choice is supported by the fact that from the FE mode shapes, the lateral modes are quite distinct from vertical modes and the torsional modes are not considered. In fact, the building model has been simplified to 2D frame.

Two modal cases that contain a limited number of modes are considered. The modal case A is with three first modes. The modal case B is with six modes shapes, in which modes from 3 to 6 have main modal displacement in the vertical directions. The limited number of modes selected for both cases are favourable to the condition of the problem as the numbers of sensor are at least equal to the contributing modes in order to avoid singularity in the Fisher information matrix. Both cases are designed for bi-axial accelerometers.

6.1.3.2.1 Design for the modal case A

An information entropy index (IEI) is introduced as a normalized value to compare the difference between any configuration to the reference configuration where all possible locations in the pre-defined mesh are equipped with sensors:

$$\text{IEI} = \left[\frac{\det Q(L_{ref}, \theta_0, \Sigma)}{\det Q(L, \theta_0, \Sigma)} \right]^{1/2}$$

IEI is a function of three variables that are unknown in the design stage. It depends on the number of sensors employed, their configuration and the prediction error correlation matrix among different channels. A large value of IEI means that the information content is small in relation to reference configuration. IEI should go down to unity as the number of sensors deployed approaches the reference mesh.

The minimum information entropy values for Case A as a function of the number of sensors computed by the FSSP and BSSP algorithms are shown in Figure 119. Since bi-axial sensors are used, at least two sensors are needed in order to make the condition of the problem well posed. If three sensors are used, the configuration is shown in Figure 120. Since lateral vibration is dominant in this modal case, two are positioned at the top level and the third floor, respectively. One sensor is place between the first and the second floor. This is because the potential measurement grid is planned for many points along the vertical direction of the column.

If 5 sensors are used two are positioned at the top floor (Figure 121). These two sensors are positioned far beyond the correlation length as set by 2 m in the algorithm. If 15 sensors are used, they tend to distribute all over the building frames. No sensor is found

in the column between the ground floor and the first floor, probably due to the low level of vibration in this area.

6.1.3.2.2 Design for the modal case B

In the modal case B, at least three sensors are needed to avoid the singularity of the Fisher information matrix. The information entropy index as a function of the number of sensor is given in Figure 123. The BSSP algorithm gives more accurate IEI value, especially if there are less than five sensors. This difference could be due to the nature of FSSP and BSSP algorithms. The IEI approaches unity as the number of sensors closes to the proposed measurement grid.

If three sensors are used, two are positioned in the beam and one is positioned in the column (Figure 124). If five sensors are used they follows the same trend because sensors are positioned in beams are also able to measure the column vibration (Figure 125). The more sensors are deployed, they are distributed all over the structure (Figure 126 and Figure 127).

Figure 119: The information entropy index of the modal case A with the correlation length of 2 m.

Figure 120: OSL of the modal case A with 3 sensors.

Figure 121: OSL of the modal case A with 5 sensors.

Figure 122: OSL of the modal case A with 15 sensors.

Figure 123: The information entropy index of the modal case B with the correlation length of 2 m.

Figure 124: OSL of the modal case B with 3 sensors.

Figure 125: OSL of the modal case B with 5 sensors.

Figure 126: OSL of the modal case B with 15 sensors.

Figure 127: OSL of the modal case B with 20 sensors.

6.2 The use of advanced sensing technology in vibration based testing.

Important factors, especially in ambient vibration testing, are the choice of sensors (type, sensitivity) and its covered frequency interval. Often, ambient measurement can only deliver quantitatively good information of the lower modes. A way to extend the frequency interval is the use of a (rather small) artificial excitation source, extra to the ambient disturbances. Otherwise, forced vibration test must be performed. In this case proper sensors and signal conditioning are important but not a major problem because the intensity of the signals to be measured is high and remains more or less constant. Nevertheless, the force excitation level should be high enough to prevail upon the ambient influences.

High resolution analogue-to-digital (ADC) conversion rate, e.g. 24-bit ADC, is preferred to cope with various signal levels without risking a bad signal-to-noise ratio of frequent saturation of the ADC. Nowadays, advance technology allows for sensors with a high sensitivity and a high resolution (a very low internal noise level).

6.2.1 The use of wireless sensors: synchronization issue.

In comparison to the relatively high cost and time consuming associated with wired structural monitoring systems, the use of wireless sensors is advantageous in terms of simple configuration and rapid deployment. Recently, wireless sensors have gained popularity in the civil engineering community [Cunha et al., 2006; Ceriotti et al., 2009; He et al., 2012]. Wireless acquisition systems are often assembled from wireless sensor units that combine sensing, data acquisition and communication capacities in a single device.

Figure 128: Wireless synchronisation with GPS time and Ethernet link (GeoSig GMS-18 sensor).

Time synchronization is the most important issues, since asynchronous data have significant effects on identified mode shapes, though their effects on the identified frequencies and damping ratios are negligible [Lei et al., 2005]. There are two types of time synchronization problems to be addressed: the first one is clock deviation, which is shown as non-uniform sampling intervals within a single unit. The second one is spatial jitter, which is characterized by time-synchronization errors among different devices. The clock deviation problem can often be solved by using a time clock with high accuracy. The intelligent real-time clock with self-learning temperature compensation is often synchronized with GPS or Internet Time Protocol to provide high timing accuracy (Figure 128). On the other hand, a spatial jitter problem can usually be solved by deploying time synchronous Wi-Fi network.

6.2.2 Remote sensing technology.

Remote sensing devices can be directed at targets that are difficult to access or to attach a (conventional) physical transducer. Another advantage is to make the vibration measurement without added mass to structures.

The two most common technologies applicable to building constructions are the laser Doppler vibrometer (LDV) and the radar technique. A single point laser vibrometer can measure a very long distance. The laser beam from the LDV is directed at the surface of interest, and the vibration amplitude and frequency are extracted from the Doppler shift of the laser beam frequency due to the motion of the surface. The output of an LDV is generally a continuous analogue voltage that is directly proportional to the target velocity component along the direction of the laser beam. Figure 129 gives an example of vibration measurement of a TV tower. It is a 300-m free standing tower in Saint-Pieters-Leeuw on the outskirts of Brussels. The distance from the laser sensing device to the tower is 221m.

Figure 129: Polytec's RSV-150 to measure a TV tower near Brussels (a);
Satellite view of the tower extracted from Google Earth (b).

In seismic monitoring, sometimes, buildings are considered as a single degree-of-freedom. The use of remote sensing technique is advantageous at large scale, e.g. to measure many structures at regional level.

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